

Can We Reverse Global Warming?

1. Abstract

Without mitigation, Climate Change is expected to cost large amounts of money, cause vast amounts of human suffering and death and threatens the survival of countless species. Rising global temperatures alone are expected to cause a drop in GDP of 30 – 70% for many countries with already high temperatures. In combination with other factors (population growth, increasing water stress, coastal flooding, loss of coastal land, increasing forest fires, loss of wildlife areas and insufficient wild-life corridors), Climate Change could lead to a collapse in ecosystem services, estimated at almost twice the global GDP. For humans, these combined factors would increase poverty, famine, starvation and cause mass migration. Under the Paris Accord, countries agreed to limit Climate Change to 1.5 degrees. This limit was not set because it was a “safe” for biodiversity or humanity, but because lower limits were considered “unachievable”. However, a relatively quick reversal of global warming would minimize all damages that would occur over the next centuries under Climate Change. Besides the return to pre-industrial atmospheric conditions, minimizing loss of human lives and minimizing damage to wildlife areas and the biodiversity these represent, this would also allow a gradual restoration of mountain snow and ice caps, restoring melt water flows, reduce water stress and minimize coastal flooding. Governments treat the changes needed to transition to a carbon neutral world as “costs” instead of “investments”. Here I show how the use of renewable energy (especially roof PV solar), ground source heat pumps and electric cars combined with massive application of direct air capture and sequestration of CO₂ (DACCS) can reverse global warming in 40 to 60 years while saving massive amounts of money (about 3.62% of GDP). A critical element in doing this is the use of the Impacts Measurement and Conservation System (IMACS) as the business model. The IMACS system puts consumers, retailers and organizations in general in charge of selling and buying incrementally less damaging and more sustainable products and services, while being rewarded for their actions. Under IMACS, current and historic damaging impacts are calculated and assigned to participating products, services and individual labor. For participating sellers, damaging impacts and associated sustainabilities are accurately calculated per product and service per sales location (and daily adjusted) using automated and low costs methods. For non-participating competitor products, the impacts cannot be calculated accurately and are set to the statistic upper damage limit for each damage type for the product group. Sellers who start participation will therefore almost always see large reductions in damaging impacts and large increases in reported sustainabilities for their products and services. This could dramatically accelerate the rate of change towards a sustainable world. Participation in IMACS is voluntary and cost-free for individuals. In order for products to become (more) sustainable, damaging impacts like greenhouse gas emissions must be eliminated or not be offset by CO₂ sequestered in permanent storage locations. For the society as a whole, becoming carbon neutral saves large amounts of money compared to not doing so, even when the costs of CO₂ sequestration are included. Under IMACS, the purchase of neutralizing amounts of sequestered CO₂ are paid for during the product purchase with an electronic voucher provided by the retailer. This only applies to participating products and services sold by participating retailers to participating customers. For a 40-year global warming reversal period, the average DACCS costs for the base and conservative DACCS cost scenarios are respectively 0.65 – 1.78% of GDP, but drop to 0.26 – 0.73% of GDP over 100 years. For carbon neutral sellers, the average DACCS costs (neutralizing historic emissions) are 0.92 – 2.56% of sale, but reach 1.58 – 4.39% of sale for the peak year. The ratio of cumulative energy cost savings over cumulative DACCS costs for a 40-year global warming reversal are 1.6 - 4.4 over the 40-year period and 4.5 – 12.4 over 100-year. Early participating sellers will receive all or most of these savings. Since under IMACS, the saving from carbon neutral operations throughout the supply chain go hand in hand with the DACCS payments for remaining and historical CO₂ emissions, the DACCS costs can be paid out of the savings from carbon neutral operations. The compound annual growth rate (CAGR) for the DACCS industry, as needed to reverse global warming, is in line with the currently expected CAGR for the DACCS industry between 2023 and 2032 (42 – 70% on production basis). A 63% growth rate under default model conditions maintained for 26 years would lead to global warming reversal in model year 41. By participating in IMACS, individuals and organizations can eliminate current CO₂ emissions, neutralize historic CO₂ emissions, save money and improve their competitive position. Becoming sustainable can be simplified from a political to a marketing challenge. IMACS, by assigning the costs of conservation (protection and restoration) to individuals and organizations responsible for the damage done, can effectively address and solve the classic “tragedy of the commons”.

2. Introduction

Anthropogenic greenhouse gasses emitted since the start of the industrial revolution (~ year 1750) have led to atmospheric CO₂ concentrations that are now about 50% higher than in 1750. This has led to significant global warming. Continued anthropogenic greenhouse gas emissions will further increase global warming with disastrous effects for both wildlife and humanity: biodiversity loss, sea level rise, more variable weather patterns (more storms and more damage) and increased crop failures, ultimately leading to tremendous human suffering. Of all potential mitigation scenarios, two stand out: A: *A rapid phaseout of greenhouse gas emissions* and B: *Direct Air Capture and Sequestration (DACCS)*. The effects of scenario A were extensively modeled. For most models the average global temperature stopped rising after a few decades, but continued to rise in others for decades. Thereafter, temperatures started to fall very slowly. In one model where CO₂ emissions were ceased by 2030 and intended to limit global temperature rise by 1.5 °C, the global temperature dropped by 0.5 °C by 2100, while temperature would still be 0.5 °C above normal in year 2300. Global cooling to pre-industrial conditions could possibly take as long as to year 3000. (34). Under those conditions the above damage to wildlife and humanity would be highly likely. That is different for a combination of scenarios A and B, where the use of DACCS would allow a much faster return to pre-industrial atmospheric conditions, preventing most of the damage to wildlife and humanity. A unique system of methods was designed to calculate environmental and human condition impacts of offerings (products and services) and individuals and apply conservation to neutralize the impacts (87, 1-8). IMACS participation is voluntary. Using this Impact Measurement and Conservation System (IMACS), the environmental impacts for products and services can be determined in a highly automated fashion and at low costs. Using the market costs of environmental conservation, the costs of environmental resource use, protection and restoration can be calculated (8). While the system is designed to ultimately address all environmental and human condition impacts, for this text I limit the application of IMACS to the capture and sequestration of atmospheric CO₂. In this article I will use the emission and removal of CO₂ to and from the atmosphere as an example to show how effective the IMAC system can mitigate all environmental impacts over a relatively short period. Global warming is caused by increased atmospheric concentrations of greenhouse gasses, in particular of CO₂ and methane. Methane reacts in the atmosphere to CO₂ and water with a half-life of 8.6 year (11) and can then be removed as CO₂. Comparing all types of conservation needed to return to a sustainable world (4), the removal of CO₂ from the atmosphere is the by far most costly conservation aspect. The Paris Agreement, the United Nations, the World Economic Forum and the Scientific Community all support the objective to limit global warming to 1.5 °C. However, even 1.5 °C of global warming will cause massive and ongoing biodiversity losses. I therefore set an improved objective to return to pre-industrial atmospheric conditions and reverse global warming in the shortest time possible. Governments and most of society have thus far seen spending on climate change mitigation as a cost instead of an investment with an attractive return. Here, I will show that the reversal of global warming is not only possible, but can be done saving more money than the cost of mitigation, as long as the transition to a renewable energy society is done in a smart way. The release of CO₂ is easily measured while various direct air capture and storage (DACCS) processes are available for scale-up to commercial scale, once sufficient market demand exists. Although the technology to remove CO₂ from the atmosphere is not yet mature and still expensive, the technology is continuously improving and expected to get much cheaper in the near future. After capture from air, the CO₂ can be stored permanently underground, preferable in deep basaltic formations, where more than 80 % mineralizes within 2 years (17). CO₂ is injected with water into the basaltic reservoir. The estimated cost of storing and transporting a ton of CO₂ at maximum reservoir exploitation via dissolved water injection is about \$17 (17). Over the last decade, a number of pilot scale DAC facilities were built using a variety of processes (50). An increasing number of larger DACCS projects are now under construction or received grants. [Project Bison](#) (50) in Wyoming aims to capture 5 million-ton CO₂ per year (5 MtCO₂/y) by year 2050. The first phase, expected to be completed in 2023, aims to capture 12,000 tCO₂/y. The US DOE on Aug 11 2023 announced over \$1 billion in federal grants for [Project Cypres](#) (50) in Louisiana, which has the potential to remove up to 30 MtCO₂/y (79). A detailed cost estimate for a commercial scale (1 MtCO₂/y) DACCS facility using the Carbon-Engineering technology was estimated to capture CO₂ at levelized costs of 92 - 232 \$/tCO₂ (9). Costs for currently used (older) and smaller scale commercial DACCS processes can be much higher, but US DOE expect costs to drop over time to 20 \$/tCO₂ (10) for improved and larger scale processes. Using the IMAC system, the CO₂ emissions for a selected fraction of offerings sold, can be fully offset (neutralized) by carbon sequestration through the purchase of carbon sequestration certificates. While purchased by participating buyers, the costs are paid by participating sellers in the form of environmental vouchers, but only for sales of so called “participating offerings” to “participating buyers”. With each purchase of a participating product or service, the participating buyer automatically buys the sequestered CO₂ amount matching the equivalent CO₂ emissions of the product or service. Since the conservation capacity is limited and differs for each impact variable, the IMACS organization needs to set

the fraction of sales (participating offerings) for which conservation must be applied for each impact variable. These fractions are daily updated such that the various conservation industries sell 100% of their conservation product. The IMAC system implements the purchase of the CO₂ captured and sequestered using the E-voucher provided by the seller. The objectives of IMACS with respect to carbon sequestration are two-fold:

1. Add a cost to products and labor for each amount of CO₂ emitted that is not offset by sequestration of the same amount of CO₂. These added costs are equal to the market cost of sequestration of the amount of CO₂ emitted. This has the following effects:
 - a. It creates an incentive to prevent CO₂ emissions: for zero CO₂ emissions, these costs drop to zero.
 - b. The savings from transitioning to carbon neutral systems will become larger, leading to a faster rate of such transitions and a more competitive marketplace (participants will save money, while non-participants will lose market share).
2. Create condition where the DACCS industry can grow at its highest rate.
 - a. With the IMACS organization setting the fraction of sales for which CO₂ sequestration needs to be applied, the DACCS industry can grow at the maximum rate at which DACCS facilities can be built.
 - b. An exponentially increasing amount of CO₂ can be sequestered, such that global carbon neutrality can be reached much sooner than otherwise possible.

The current process of transitioning to a carbon neutral society, with its slow political adoption of carbon neutral standards, the lack of sufficient financial incentive to speed up this transition and the inhibition of such transition by stakeholders with monopoly positions is referred to as the “Business As Usual” (BAU) conditions. The implementation of DACCS systems at scales sufficient to reverse global warming or to limit global warming to 1.5 degree C, is mainly caused by the high cost of carbon sequestration. The IMAC system aims to provide ample funding for DACCS, both jumpstarting and accelerating DACCS implementation.

3. Removing Atmospheric CO₂

In this document I want to test the hypothesis that we can reverse global warming in about 50 years and at costs comparable to the medium-term energy savings from switching to renewable energy sources. Global warming is caused by the anthropogenic release of greenhouse gasses (mostly CO₂ and Methane). A large fraction of the CO₂ emitted to the atmosphere is absorbed by oceans leading to acidification. Global warming and ocean acidification lead to large biodiversity losses (50). Earth has a limited capacity to absorb CO₂ in an environmentally safe way in existing and new wildlife areas (mostly forests). Landscape change has drastically reduced the global forest area (27). However, even given the current use of cultivated areas, the carbon stored in global forests is significantly below its natural potential (12). In case humans would never have burnt fossil fuels, not have eroded or damaged soils, and humans would disappear from Earth, forest would regrow on all areas where it grew in the recent past. This would lower the atmospheric and oceanic CO₂ concentrations until pre-industrial conditions are reached. In that case Earth’s flora, fauna and climate would return (after centuries) to an approximation of the conditions prior to year 1750. Unfortunately, by 2022 the cumulative CO₂ emissions due to the burning of fossil fuels are more than twice the emissions due to landscape change (see table 5.1). To sequester all the CO₂ released would require “multiple planets Earth” to provide the forest area needed to sequester all carbon in order to return relatively quickly (a few centuries) to pre-industrial conditions. Without “multiple planets Earth”, atmospheric CO₂ concentrations would reduce much slower via ocean absorption and transport to the deep ocean (50) and the remaining higher temperatures would continue high rates of biodiversity losses. Currently more than eight billion humans live on Earth and the population is still growing. A large fraction of land is in use by humans and no longer available to grow forests. Even after including the sequestration of wood used for longer periods (buildings), the harvesting cycle of commercial forests is a cause for CO₂ emissions compared to the CO₂ stored in their previous stands of old growth forest (13, 16). These effects further increase the number of planets Earth needed to return to pre-industrial atmospheric conditions using C-sequestration using forests alone. However, humanity could completely stop the burning of all fossil fuels, of organic waste materials and stop the use of landfills and starkly reduce or stop the use of wood. If a complete stop would be reached and maintained, a fraction of all historic CO₂ emissions currently stored in the atmospheric and in oceanic carbon sinks could be captured by trees and stored in a growing area of increasingly carbon denser “reserve” forests, which could never be cut. Since 1750, the atmospheric CO₂ concentration rose from 278 to 420 ppm in Dec 2023. This 50% increase in atmospheric CO₂ allowed plants to grow faster and is referred to as the “CO₂ fertilization” effect (14, 15). The forest carbon density has increased due to CO₂ fertilization, resulting in a large additional storage of CO₂ in forests (compared to the 1750 amount) even after more

than half of all global forests were replaced by human cultivated lands (meadows, crop-fields and built-up areas). Even without global warming the world would face biodiversity losses, water stress, soil erosion and the damaging effects of air and water pollution. Global warming exacerbates these effects. Elevated global temperatures would lead to an additional loss of biodiversity, significant sea level rise and changing weather patterns with more heavy storms (1st order effects). Global warming also has indirect (2nd order) effects. Sea level rise does not have to lead to flooding in case adequate dike systems are built. However, in most parts of the world such funding is not available. Floodings will result in loss of coastal wildlife areas and crop fields, forcing human populations to move further inland and to lands not already in use by others. Other 2nd order effects are the increasing lack of fresh water due to the disappearance of glaciers, a further change of weather patterns like droughts and heat waves, an increase in poor or failed harvests and a further worsening of storms. The combined effects are likely to result in increased human suffering and death due to heat, lack of fresh water, famine, disease, flooding and forced relocation. The transition to a sustainable society requires many large changes. The overarching one is the conservation of biodiversity by protecting, expanding and restoring wildlife areas in all global ecoregions. However, this is impossible under conditions of continuing global warming due to the change of climatic conditions under which the ecoregion developed. Many species would need to move to cooler areas to survive, while bordering areas are cultivated and not available as wildlife areas. Not only do we need to stop emitting global warming gasses, we need to remove a large fraction of all anthropogenic CO₂ historically emitted to limit global warming levels where global biodiversity can be preserved. However, even a 1.5 °C mean global warming will result in massive biodiversity losses, a drastic increase in water scarcity, increase in storm damage, sea level rise and the flooding of loss of low-lying lands and the associated massive human migration, human suffering and loss of life (50). Removal of atmospheric CO₂ to year 1750 would create global forcing conditions equivalent to year 1750. Since only the top 2 meter of land changes temperature with the seasons, and due to the low specific heat of soil compared to water, temperatures above land will quickly drop to pre-industrial conditions (50). This is not the case for ocean temperatures, due to the mixing of heat into deeper ocean layers and the high specific heat of water. It will probably take centuries for the oceans to cool down to pre-industrial conditions. The restoration of snow and ice packs and the associated melt water flows would only very slowly be restored. It might be better to remove CO₂ to just below pre-industrial concentrations to allow ocean and land masses to cool faster and allow a faster restoration to the best remaining approximation of pre-industrial conditions.

4. Current Carbon Fluxes

Data for carbon fluxes from emission sources and their storage in sinks, as needed for modeling, are reported by Friedlingstein et al. 2022 (20). Carbon fluxes vary annually, but especially 2020 was an abnormal year. Global fossil fuel emissions dropped due to COVID-19, while landscape change emissions dropped as well. The data reported in 2022 included 2020 as the last year. The fossil emissions for 2021 and 2022 were calculated using trend lines. Changing forests to crop fields or meadows, releases large amounts of CO₂ referred to as “land-use change emissions”. The flux due to land-use change, ocean sink flux and land sink flux were calculated using 2nd order polynomials (51). For the flux resulting from atmospheric growth, a linear trend line was used (51). For the cement carbonation sink flux, a linear trend line over the 2011 to 2020 period was used (51). See table 4.1. (52)

Year	Fossil Emissions Excluding Carbonation	Land-Use Change Emissions	Atmospheric Growth	Ocean Sink Growth	Land Sink Growth	Cement Carbonation Sink Growth
2021	10.3408	0.972	5.243	3.095	3.061	0.2239
2022	10.4756	0.944	5.307	3.161	3.062	0.2291

Table 4.1: Carbon flux values used in the calculation model for year 2021 and year 2022. All values in gigaton carbon per year (GtC/y). All values are calculated from source data by Friedlingstein et al. 2022 (20). See summary tab with a full list of contributors in this source material. Charts with trend lines and their equations are added to a modified copy of the Historical Budget tab of the original Excel file Global_Carbon_Budget_2021v1.0.xlsx (Friedlingstein et al. 2022 (20)), renamed as “Global_Carbon_Budget_2021v1.0-1.xlsx” (51, 53).

5. Carbon Sources and Sinks

CO₂ is emitted by sources and absorbed by sinks. Sources are fossil fuel emissions and land-use change emissions, while the atmosphere, remaining forests, the oceans and concrete are carbon sinks. With the start of the industrial revolution, populations grew and more agricultural area was needed. Consequently, forests were increasingly cleared and these areas were cultivated (land-use change). The standing timber felled was used for construction or was burnt directly as firewood. Over time essentially all wood and a large fraction of the underground root mass was ultimately converted to CO₂ and water. In addition, fossil fuels were increasingly burnt. The CO₂ emitted due to land-use change and burning of fossil fuels is mostly stored in the atmosphere (299 GtC), in remaining forested areas (222 GtC) and in the oceans (183 GtC). Over the last 10,000 years ago, Earth has lost 33% of its forest and 27% since year 1700 (50). See [table 5.1](#).

Fossil Emissions Excluding Carbonation	Land-Use Change Emissions	Atmospheric Growth	Ocean Sink	Land Sink	Cement Carbonation Sink	Budget Imbalance
483.82	203.68	298.95	184.82	222.34	5.62	25.75
70.4%	29.6%	42.0%	26.0%	31.2%	0.8%	3.7%
687.5		711.74				
687.5		483.77		227.97		25.75
70.4%	29.6%	68.0%		32.0%		3.7%

Table 5.1: Cumulative historic Carbon Budget 1750 to 2022. Data for 2021 and 2022 are extrapolated. All values in gigaton carbon (GtC). All values are calculated from source data by [Friedlingstein et al. 2022 \(20\)](#).

The data in [table 5.1](#) show the cumulative CO₂ source and sink data from 1750 to 2022, while [table 5.2](#) shows the cumulative data for the decade from 2011 to 2020, to allow calculation of recent annual averages. Comparing [tables 5.1 and 5.2](#), it is important to recognize that 90% of the recent decadal carbon emissions result from fossil fuels, versus 70% over the 272-year period since 1750. The recent land-use change emissions dropped from 30% over the 272-year period to 10% of total emissions over the last decade. The fraction of recent carbon emissions absorbed in the atmosphere increases by 3 to 5%. The fraction of recent carbon emissions absorbed in the land sink reduced slightly (28% versus 31%), while the recent fraction of the carbon emissions absorbed in the ocean sink remained essentially unchanged (25% versus 26%). The data in [tables 5.1 and 5.2](#) are used in the CO₂ mass balance model.

Fossil Emissions Excluding Carbonation	Land-Use Change Emissions	Atmospheric Growth	Ocean Sink	Land Sink	Cement Carbonation Sink	Budget Imbalance
96.96	11.30	50.61	27.80	30.63	1.97	-2.75
89.6%	10.4%	45.6%	25.0%	27.6%	1.8%	-3%
108.26		111.01				
108.26		78.41		32.60		-2.75
90%	10%	71%		29%		-3%

Table 5.2: Cumulative historic CO₂ Budget for the decade from 2011 to 2020. All values in gigaton carbon (GtC). All values are calculated from source data by [Friedlingstein et al. 2022 \(20\)](#).

6. System Dynamics

6.1. Land Sink Fluxes

Plants require light, water, nutrients and favorable temperatures to grow. Plants react rather quickly to CO₂ changes in surrounding air. Results from greenhouses show a response in growth rate to a change in CO₂ concentrations within hours (29). Due to plant respiration and microbial activities, the CO₂ level is higher at night. However, this accumulated CO₂ is absorbed during the first hours of daylight. During daytime photosynthesis, the CO₂ level may drop from 400 to 150-200 ppm in a sealed greenhouse. An increase in ambient CO₂ to 800 - 1,000 ppm can increase yield for C3 plants up to 40% – 100% and for C4 plants by 10% – 25% while keeping other inputs at an optimum level (29). At higher CO₂ concentrations, the normal fertilizer rate can be exhausted quickly and plants may show nutrient deficiency symptoms. Some micro nutrients like sink and iron may be depleted more quickly than macro nutrients (29). At constant CO₂ concentration and rising temperatures, the CO₂ absorption rate rises to and optimum. Adding CO₂ one to two hours after sunrise and stopping two to three hours before sunset was found to be the ideal duration of supplementation (29). At higher CO₂ concentrations, a higher optimum CO₂ absorption rate is found at a higher temperature (30). Since the start of the industrial revolution, about 31% of all CO₂ emitted has accumulated in the atmosphere (table 5.1). The atmospheric CO₂ concentration rose from 278 ppm in 1750, to 418 ppm in 2020. Just over 70% of this accumulation took place over the last 60 years, rising from 318 to 418 ppm (See figure 6.1). Of all CO₂ emitted, about 31% is stored in the land sink as additional terrestrial biomass (table 5.1). Forests store 92% of all terrestrial biomass (25).

Figure 6.1.: Accumulation of CO₂ in the atmosphere as percentage of the 2022 total. Of all anthropogenic CO₂ accumulated since 1750, 70% accumulated over the last 60 years. This 60-year period is short compared to the average natural lifetime of trees in the tropics (186 years) and outside the tropics (322 years). The atmospheric CO₂ concentration rose from 278 ppm in 1750 to 318 in 1960 and to 413 ppm in 2022 (right). All values are calculated from source data by Friedlingstein *et al.* 2022 (20).

Under otherwise favorable conditions, current and future elevated atmospheric CO₂, can lead to an increase in the aboveground biomass (AGB), but higher temperature in the tropics (28) and draughts (54) associated with climate change, may lead to negative net primary production (NPP) due to reduced gross primary production (GPP) and increased respiration. Over the 20th century, the GPP was estimated to be about 31% higher than historical levels and is attributed to CO₂ fertilization (22). Model simulations for the 21st century result in the smallest r.m.s error for a GPP growth 50% higher than historical levels, but GPP growth may be lower once nutrient limitations are parameterized for future simulations (22). Although varying for different forest types, the global aboveground net primary productivity (ANPP) is approximately half of the global GPP (24). For ANPP values below 20 Mg Ha⁻¹ y⁻¹, the above ground biomass (AGB) increases with increasing ANPP (23). The carbon density for all forests types has increased over the period 1990 to 2007 (23). Most of the CO₂ emitted since 1750 and stored in forests was stored there over the last 80 years (figure 6.2 left section). Since 1940, the land sink CO₂ accumulation was approximately linear (figure 6.2B). This took place under conditions where the global forest area reduced by 4.1 to 6.4 M Ha y⁻¹ over recent decades (27). On average higher global temperatures will allow trees to grow faster in colder areas or allow tree growth in even colder area where no trees grew over the last centuries. With rising global temperatures, the AGB will likely increase in the average global forest with a possible reduction of AGB in tropical areas above yet unknown temperatures (28). A recent study showed that tropical forests, degraded by deforestation, fire and drought, are nearly carbon neutral, while boreal and temperate forests have become the main global carbon sinks (31). Another study found evidence that boreal forests have become net CO₂ emitters since the 1980s (32). On a

global scale, under current and rising atmospheric CO₂ concentrations, forests will continue to grow and store carbon to higher carbon densities, where the carbon density is a function of temperature, atmospheric CO₂ concentration and duration and land area available for forests. The large land area with relatively low population density in the Northern section of the Northern hemisphere would allow temperate forests to grow and would provide a large carbon sink, as long as such forests are not cut. Based on the above, under current and rising atmospheric CO₂ conditions, the trend in annual CO₂ fluxes to the global land sink is likely to continue over the next few decades (22).

Figure 6.2. A: Annual carbon flux to the land sink between 1750 and 2022. B: Since 1940, the land sink absorptions increased roughly linear with time. Data calculated using data from Friedlingstein *et al.* 2022 (20).

In order to reverse global warming, we need to reverse the current net CO₂ emission to net C-sequestrations. Such a reversal must start with a year over year reduction of anthropogenic CO₂ emissions, further aided by continuously increasing annual CO₂ sequestrations using technical means like DACCS. To reverse acidification of the ocean surface layer and to stop the associated loss of ocean biodiversity, we would need to remove the CO₂ currently stored there as well. However, the reverse process can back track the historical path. The land surface area needed to regrow the original forests is no longer available, since it is used as human cultivated area, while temperate forests store carbon lost by tropical rain forests at lower density (23). Reduction of anthropogenic CO₂ emissions and increase of DACCS capacity will start slow and will initially have no to little effect on atmospheric CO₂. The atmospheric CO₂ concentration would initially still rise, reach a maximum and drop from there to year 1750 conditions. For the reverse process I assume that the same linear relation for the land sink flux as function of the atmospheric CO₂ concentration applies. In that case, the land sink flux would first increase and later reduce until reaching zero at the 278 ppm CO₂ corresponding to year 1750 conditions. Figure 6.3A shows the historic global land sink flux as function of the atmospheric CO₂ concentration. Five-year averages are used for the land sink flux to reduce the large annual variability and better visualize the trend. The recent annual carbon flux to the land sink of 3 GtC/y reflects the essentially instant response of plants to the elevated (then 404 ppm) atmospheric CO₂ concentration. On a global scale such fluxes are primarily a function of atmospheric CO₂ concentration and forest area available (23). Due to the quick response of plants to CO₂, fluxes to the land sink will almost immediately increase or reduce once atmospheric CO₂ concentrations rise or drop. The trendline would have been steeper if much less or no landscape change would have taken place since 1750. The land sink was defined/set to zero for year 1750 and the land sink fluxes were estimated to rise gradually above zero, due to the then still very small increases in atmospheric CO₂ (20). For the business as usual (BAU) case of an approximately linear increase of atmospheric CO₂ over time, forests growth may be increasingly limited in some areas due to limited availability of nutrients, water and light. For the case of dropping atmospheric CO₂ concentrations, such limitation will become increasingly smaller. For continuously dropping atmospheric CO₂ concentrations, trees will continue to grow, but less fast and the CO₂ flux to the land sink will annually reduce roughly according to the trendline in figure 6.3A (55). Once year 1750 atmospheric CO₂ conditions are reached, the world's tree will still grow but the CO₂ flux to the land sink will become zero. All land sink biomass now stored in live trees will over time be released as CO₂ due to microbial processes. Trees take a long time to mature and can live a long time; 186 +/- 137 year in the tropics and 322 +/- 201 year outside the tropics (21). A fraction of trees continues to stand for many years after they die. In one study where Scots pine, Norway Spruce and Silver Birch were compared, 50% of trees were still standing as snags 17 to 21 years after death, while 50% of their stem mass remained 14 to 35 years after death (33). While the anthropogenic carbon is stored now, most of the decay and associated CO₂ emissions of this additional stored carbon (the land sink) will

only be released as CO₂ after two to three hundred years. This means that for very slow rates of C-sequestration using DACCS (lasting much longer than 322 years), the entire land sink amount would need to be sequestered, while for high rates (lasting much shorter than 200 years), none of the land sink CO₂ amount would need to be sequestered using DACCS.

Figure 6.3: A: Land + cement sink fluxes as function of the atmospheric CO₂ concentration over the 1750 to 2020 period. Under conditions of constant forest area, the land sink flux increase would have been steeper. To smooth the land flux data, five-year averages are used. B: Cumulative land sink versus atmospheric CO₂ concentration. All values are calculated from source data by Friedlingstein *et al.* 2022 (20).

As long as the period needed to return to pre-industrial atmospheric conditions is much shorter than the average life of the world's trees, the additional fraction of CO₂ emitted originating from the land sink can be ignored. Based on the above it would be reasonable to assume that under conditions of large scale DACCS, the annual land sink flux will reduce as a linear reduction with atmospheric CO₂, until it reaches zero under year 1750 atmospheric CO₂ conditions. This linear function (figure 6.3A) will be used in the model.

One large positive aspect of this is that hardly any of the CO₂ absorbed in the land sink since 1750 needs to be removed using DACCS prior to reaching year 1750 atmospheric conditions if the sequestration takes place over a relatively short period (say 40 – 60 years). If the time needed to reduce the atmospheric CO₂ using DACCS is much shorter than the turnover time of forests, most of the CO₂ captured by forests will continue to be stored as the “land sink”, for many decades to centuries. Once year 1750 atmospheric conditions are reached, a small fraction of the by then installed DACCS equipment will suffice to sequestering the forest CO₂ vent flows caused by microbial degradation of “land sink carbon” over the following two to three centuries, while maintaining the new low atmospheric CO₂ conditions required to create the optimum global cooling conditions.

6.2. Ocean Sink Fluxes

For aqueous CO₂ in a well-mixed aerated system at steady state conditions, the CO₂ concentration in the gas phase above the water is in equilibrium with the CO₂ concentration of the water [CO₂]. The ratio of these two can be described by Henry's law as $H_v = P_{CO_2} / [CO_2]$. However, the system representing the atmosphere and oceans is much more complex with dissolved CO₂, the non-dissociated carbonic acid H₂CO₃, the anions HCO₃⁻, CO₃²⁻, the non-dissociated calcium carbonate CaCO₃, cations H⁺, Na⁺, Mg²⁺, Ca²⁺ and all their associated equilibrium reactions (3) (56). In addition, oceans are poorly mixed, especially vertically. Mixing mainly takes place in the “mixed layer”, the top 1/50 of the water column (~ 75 m), while vertical mixing with deeper ocean layers is poor. We can further envision this “mixed” layer as multiple sub-layers. From a physical point of view, even this “mixed” layer is still poorly mixed; if ideally mixed, the concentrations in all sub-layers of the mixed layer would be the same at all times. Due to these mixing limitations, equilibrium conditions with the atmosphere can only be reached for the water film in direct contact with the atmosphere. The degree of mixing within the mixed layer is mainly a function of wind speed and surface water roughness (wind speed and fetch length dependent). Of the various sub-layers within the mixed layer, the surface sub-layer has the highest mixing intensity, with gradually less mixing in the lower sub-layers. The lowest sub-layer of the mixed layer mixes to some extent with upper layer of the deep ocean. Since interactions with the atmosphere take place at the water surface, CO₂ concentrations gradually drop from close to saturation at the water surface sub-layer to CO₂ concentrations approximating those of the deep ocean in the sub-

layer bordering the top of the deep ocean (57). The surface CO₂ concentration averaged over all oceans was 56 μmol/kg (in 1994), versus 5 μmol/kg at the average global depth of 1000 m (35). CO₂ saturation and water temperature are strongly correlated; colder water with a CO₂ concentration below saturation can become saturated when the water temperature increases. With global warming, water temperatures are rising (especially in surface sub-layer), limiting the amount of CO₂ that can be absorbed, or leading to CO₂ venting when oversaturation conditions are reached. CO₂ absorption by oceans is neither constant geographically or over time. *“The amounts of CO₂ absorbed or vented vary with the phase and shifts of the North Atlantic Oscillation and the Decadal Pacific Oscillation. In addition, ozone hole induced increases in wind speeds over the Southern oceans lead to increased vertical mixing and upwellings, while rising surface water temperatures diminish the ability of ocean surface layers to absorb CO₂. In the equatorial pacific, wind driven currents and the ocean’s natural large-scale circulation drag up water from deep ocean layers to the surface at some locations. This brings up water rich in carbonates leading to CO₂ venting at the surface”* (38, 58). The warmer equatorial pacific can be venting CO₂, while at the same time the colder North Atlantic can be absorbing large amount of CO₂. The CO₂ absorption and venting fluxes of the oceanic carbon cycle are about 80 GtC/y (36) and thus much larger than the current net ocean sink absorption flux of ~ 3.0 GtC/y (36, 37). Since the ocean venting and absorbing CO₂ flux components of the pre-industrial carbon cycle were in balance, this net ocean sink absorption flux could be called the “anthropogenic ocean absorption flux”. *“At higher temperatures, ocean water can hold on to less CO₂, while vertical mixing is expected to become worse and can lead to surface layer stratification. This may lead to a future reduced ability of oceans to absorb CO₂”* (59, 60, 61, 62). It could be that the ocean venting flux increased from its pre-industrial value of 80 GtC/y to a slightly higher value (say 81 GtC/y). However, since the anthropogenic (= net) ocean absorption flux is estimated at ~ 3.0 GtC/y, the same slightly higher value would apply to the balancing component of the ocean absorption flux, resulting in the same anthropogenic ocean absorption flux (84 - 81 = 3.0 GtC/y). For simplicity, I assume that the anthropogenic ocean vent flux is currently zero (63). Using values reported by Friedlingstein *et al.* 2022 (20), the annual ocean sink CO₂ flux accelerated over the last 40 years (figure 6.4A). Plotting the CO₂ fluxes to the ocean sink since 1750 as function of the atmospheric CO₂ concentration, creates a data set that very well fits a linear trendline (figure 6.4B). On a global scale it takes the ocean surface about one year to equilibrate with the atmospheric CO₂ concentration (38). This implies that for rising atmospheric CO₂ concentrations (using the linear trendline in figure 6.2B), the ocean sink flux will have a value about 0.45% lower than the flux after equilibration (in case the atmospheric CO₂ concentration would not have increased) (64). The fully equilibrated ocean sink flux trend line would thus run slightly above the trendline in figure 6.2B. For the reverse process, the corrected trendline would run the same distance higher. Since the differences between the ocean sink flux values for the rising and dropping atmospheric CO₂ concentrations are small (less than 1%), these small differences are ignored and the same linear trendline (as in figure 6.2B), will be used for the process where CO₂ is removed from the atmosphere.

Figure 6.4A: Anthropogenic CO₂ flux from atmosphere to oceans for 1980 – 2020. **Figure 6.4B:** Anthropogenic CO₂ flux from atmosphere to oceans since 1750 as function of atmospheric CO₂ concentration. Values are based on data from Friedlingstein *et al.* 2022 (20).

Thus far, much attention was focused (60, 61, 62) on how much CO₂ the oceans can absorb under conditions of increasing atmospheric CO₂ concentrations, the associated global warming, changing weather patterns and changing ocean currents. For this article, the question changes to how mass transfer limitations between the atmosphere, the mixed layer and the deeper ocean would change the CO₂ fluxes for the reverse process where the atmospheric CO₂

concentration would rapidly reduce using DACCS at very large scales. By removing CO₂ from the atmosphere, the partial atmospheric CO₂ pressure drops; ocean sections that on average absorbed large amounts of CO₂ in the past, will likely absorb less, while sections that on average vented large amounts of CO₂ in the past, will likely vent even more. For the theoretical case of a step change in the atmospheric CO₂ from the current high (~ 418 ppm) to the low pre-industrial concentration (278 ppm), the (still) elevated CO₂ concentration in the mixed ocean layer would lead to a smaller than current anthropogenic ocean absorption flux and a larger than current ocean vent flux, leading to a net ocean vent flux. In short, the anthropogenic absorption fluxes will reduce and an anthropogenic vent flux will increase leading (over time) to a net vent flux. The linear trendline in [figure 6.4B](#) allows estimation of the anthropogenic ocean absorption flux; the anthropogenic ocean vent flux can only be calculated from the annual mass balance. For a gradual but fast reduction of atmospheric CO₂, the anthropogenic CO₂ vent flux will increase, while the anthropogenic CO₂ absorption flux will reduce until their balance leads to net ocean venting (65). However, since 1750, the ocean temperatures increased. One unresolved question is, whether for the reverse path of rapid atmospheric CO₂ reduction, the oceanic CO₂ absorption will be correctly reflected by the linear relations derived for historic atmospheric CO₂ increases and net oceanic CO₂ absorption. For the model calculations the assumption is made that it is the case.

6.3. Scenario Definition

The model will be applied to three global warming reversal periods (40, 50 and 60 years), four ocean venting scenarios and four societal participation scenarios. For all scenarios, the ocean carbon sink will be removed from only the “top layer”, but this top layer represents different fractions of the total ocean sink. For each of the four ocean venting scenarios, the transport of carbon from the deep ocean to the top ocean water layers is such that during the C-sequestration period needed to reach the case B target year:

1. 100% of the ocean sink will be vented to the atmosphere.
2. 50% of the ocean sink will be vented to the atmosphere.
3. 30% of the ocean sink will be vented to the atmosphere.
4. 10% of the ocean sink will be vented to the atmosphere.

For the societal participation scenarios

- I. The period for reaching 100% individual and 100% product participation.
- II. The period for reduction of current CO₂-emissions to zero
- III. The phase-out period for construction of additional capacity fossil fuel emission sources
- IV. The operational period for the additional capacity fossil fuel emission sources.

6.4. Case Definition

Using year 1750 as the year reflecting pre-industrial conditions, both the atmospheric and the ocean sink were defined to be zero in 1750 (36). The objective is to remove the atmospheric sink and specific scenario fraction of the ocean sink as needed to restore the pre-industrial atmospheric CO₂ concentration of 278 ppm.

Two cases (A and B) are defined, reflecting the theoretical shortest and longest periods needed for a return to pre-industrial atmospheric conditions. This period would be shorter if CO₂ mass transfer from ocean to the atmosphere (anthropogenic venting) would be strongly limited. For case A, no anthropogenic ocean venting is assumed and only the atmospheric sink needs to be removed using DACCS. The period to return to pre-industrial atmospheric conditions is therefore the shortest possible. For case B, anthropogenic ocean venting is assumed to take place and more CO₂ must be removed by more DACCS systems and the period needed to return to pre-industrial atmospheric conditions is longer. The removal of the entire ocean sink CO₂ amount would reflect the theoretical longest period for case B. The actual period needed to reach pre-industrial atmospheric conditions must lie somewhere in between the minimum (case A) and maximum (case B) periods.

Case A; No net ocean venting: The anthropogenic land sink flux is calculated using the linear relation of [figure 6.3A](#). The anthropogenic ocean CO₂ flux is calculated as function of the atmospheric CO₂ concentration using the linear relation shown in [figure 6.4B](#). This annual CO₂ flux is added to the ocean sink, while no ocean CO₂ venting takes place. The DACCS capacity needed to reach pre-industrial atmospheric CO₂ concentration for different target periods is calculated (40, 60, 80 and 100 year). Case A implies that the ocean will continue to be a sink for CO₂. No

net CO₂ venting takes place and the ocean sink will not be emptied. Instead, the ocean sink reaches its maximum CO₂ value once pre-industrial conditions are reached. This case is referred to as “No Net Ocean Venting” and is illustrated in figure 6.4.

Figure 6.5: For Case A, CO₂ is absorbed by oceans and lands, but no anthropogenic ocean or land venting of CO₂ takes place. The anthropogenic CO₂ fluxes to land and ocean are calculated using linear trendlines (Figures 6.3A and 6.4B). For Case A, CO₂ is removed from the atmosphere until pre-industrial conditions are reached, while no CO₂ is removed from the oceans (66).

Case B; Unrestricted Ocean venting: The anthropogenic CO₂ fluxes to the land sink and to the mixed ocean layer are calculated as for Case A. However, depending on the scenario, different amounts of CO₂ are assumed to represent “the removable top layer ocean sink”. For this top layer ocean sink and the atmospheric sink, CO₂ amount are assumed to be removed at rates in ratio to their remaining sink mass fractions. I.e. if the atmospheric sink would hold 300 GtC and the top 200 m ocean sink would hold 200 GtC, (respectively 60% and 40% of their combined sink amounts), then for every GtC removed using DACCS, 60% would be removed from the atmospheric sink and 40% would be removed from the top layer ocean sink. Starting with unequal sink amounts, the fractions will change over time. For Case B, the atmospheric and top layer ocean sinks would reach zero in the same year. However, since the amount of CO₂ to be removed would be much larger than for Case A, the period needed (using the same number of DACCS facilities) to reach pre-industrial atmospheric CO₂ concentrations for case B will be longer. Depending on the scenario, different fractions of CO₂ adsorbed by the ocean sink are assumed to remain in the “top” ocean layer, while the remainder is mixed into the deeper ocean. This “top” layer is further unspecified but reflects the ocean layer where CO₂ is accessible for venting. The fraction remaining in the top layer is assumed to be vented during the atmospheric restoration period, while the remaining fraction is assumed to mix into deeper ocean layers and will not be vented to the atmosphere. These fractions of the ocean sink present in the top layer will be varied from 100%, to 50%, 30% and 10%. No corresponding depths are used for these four scenarios. Case B is illustrated in figure 6.6.

Figure 6.6: For Case B, the same CO₂ fluxes to the land sink, and ocean are calculated as for case A. Using DACCS at large scales, CO₂ is vented from the top ocean layer as easily as if it were removed from the atmosphere. The amounts of CO₂ removed are proportional to the size of each sink and pre-industrial conditions for atmosphere and ocean are reached in the same year (67).

7. Methods

7.1. General

The IMACS organization needs to be funded and the various elements needed for its operation need to be created. In the actual future IMACS marketplace, individual end-user IMACS participants (hereafter simply referred to as *individual participants*) pay nothing to participate, while there will be savings in the form of lower prices offered, not available to non-participants. The individual application process is similar to applying for a personal bank account. The assumption is made that the increase in individual participation is annually sufficient and otherwise adequate to reach 100% global individual and organizational participation over the set period. With no conservation capacity available meeting IMACS requirements in model year one, and with most conservation capacity requiring investments and time, there will be a continuous shortage of conservation until pre-industrial condition are reached or otherwise best approached. Under IMACS, individual participants can buy participating product from participating retailers and buy the conservation needed to render this product (partially or fully) free of net damaging environmental impacts. Limited to CO₂ emission impacts, the customer would receive the product (partially or fully) free of net CO₂ emissions. The retailer can either become carbon neutral or pays for the costs of C-sequestration by providing an electronic voucher (E-voucher) during the same transaction process. To sell

merchandize with less carbon emissions, the retailer would have to become carbon neutral (leading to personal and business savings) and needs to switch to participating suppliers. Even in that case their products supplied will only become fully carbon neutral over time. The percentage of product participating each day will be set as a percentage of sales by the IMACS organization. This percentage is calculated by dividing the global dollar volume of DACCS CO₂ produced by the global sales volume of participating retailers. For example, if the C-sequestration capacity for 2025 is 5 MtCO₂/y available at 300 \$/tCO₂, costing 1,500 M\$/y and the global sales volume of participating retailers is 150,000 M\$/y, then the product participation percentage is calculated as $1,500 / 150,000 = 1.0\%$. Merchants can choose to apply this percentage to all product (no “participating product” is selected), or select participating product adding up to at least 1% sales. The first option is the only option available when only a few products are sold (like the few different types of gasoline at tank stations), while the 2nd option is most attractive for retailers selling hundreds or thousands of different products. For the first option, only a fraction of the CO₂ emissions for all product sold to individual participants is sequestered, while for the latter option, all CO₂ emissions are sequestered but only for the participating fraction of product sold to participant individuals. By becoming carbon neutral himself and by selecting participating product with lower CO₂ emissions, the retailer can minimize his E-voucher costs. The majority of retailers is expected to select the “participating product selection” option. With an increasing fraction of retailers selecting more sustainable product through participating suppliers, the required product participation percentage will need to be daily increased and set to a value where all globally available DACCS CO₂ is sold on a daily basis. DACCS CO₂ is considered to be available for purchase based on the volume of long-term contracts between the carbon sequestration organizations (CSOs) and the IMACS organization. Such contracts can be signed even prior to DACCS facility construction. For example, if on 1/1/2025 a contract is signed with a CSO for 10 MtCO₂/y, to be delivered starting 1/1/2029, the corresponding daily amount of additional sequestration capacity is made available for purchase the next day (on 1/2/2025). The product participation percentage will be recalculated overnight to make sure that all of the additional DACCS CO₂ capacity is pre-sold each following day. C-sequestration costs are paid based on the daily market price paid for DACCS CO₂ sequestered irrespective of the delivery date. Contract costs for future delivery are likely to be lower than the daily market price of DACCS CO₂ (and are likely to be specified in the contract to reduce over time). This creates a financial buffer allowing continuation of C-sequestration purchases during recessions when the sales volume of all product is low and the market prices of DACCS CO₂ may also be lower. All C-sequestration funds received will be held in Trust or Escrow Accounts, until each amount of DACCS CO₂ is delivered (stored in the permanent underground reservoir as agreed upon). For the above example, the Trust or Escrow Accounts would hold revenues for 4 years of production (at 100% capacity) at the day of 1st production on 1/1/2029. Similar buffers will be created for all following contracts. Under stable market conditions such buffers will stay constant or grow and are the best type of creditworthiness any CSO could hope for. Since all contracts are made at prices where the CSO is expected to make a decent profit, these capital “buffers” are likely to entice other CSOs to sign contracts for additional DACCS facilities, radically increasing DACCS capacity at growth rates that are very unlikely (if not impossible) without an end-user consumer-based purchasing and payment system as provided by IMACS. Note that while DACCS CO₂ and other CO₂ will likely be traded on international markets between businesses, the pool of DACCS CO₂ under contract between CSOs and IMACO will only be available for purchase by participating individuals buying participating product from participating retailers using the IMACS controlled systems available.

For the model used, the annual C-sequestration capacity required is calculated based on the dollar volume of participating products sold to participating end-user consumers and the C-emissions represented by these products. Customer and product participation increase from 0 to 100% over a set period with a default of 20 years. Instead of using a linear annual increase, a sigmoid function was created to better reflect a slower than linear introduction and a more gradual approach to 100% (39). Such sigmoid functions are also used for the annual reduction of current fossil emissions and for the installation of additional fossil fuel burning capacity. Including electrical power end-use, about 60% of the (2019) US greenhouse gas emissions (40) originate from the commercial & residential and the transportation sectors. This percentage would be higher if low level heating applications in agriculture were included (using GSHPs) and still higher if medium level heating applications in industry were included for which heat up to 550 °C could be provided by Stirling heat pumps (68, 69, 70). Replacing such fossil fuel applications by heat pumps, powered by wind or building mounted solar would eliminate such emissions. Heating & cooling system, cars and trucks have economic use periods of typically less than 20 years. The assumption is made that these values are similar for other developed countries. A 20-year period for phasing out fossil fuels is a good model period to use, since it allows the gradual (5% per year) replacement of the fossil fuel system with carbon neutral systems at the end of their economic use period.

Fossil CO₂ emissions will continue to increase for a while. This increase can be imagined as additional bridging capacity in new fossil fuel-based power plants, new heavy industry, new building and process heating and new

transportation systems. Over time, an increasing fraction of this additional capacity will be provided using solar and wind electric power and/or using renewable fuels (hydrogen, methane, methanol) made from DAC based CO₂ using solar and wind energy. I assume this additional fossil fuel-based fraction to reduce over time to zero. The model assumes a continuation of such fossil fuel-based power plant construction (“additional capacity”) using a construction phase-out period (20-year default) and an average operational period for such additional capacity (30-year default).

Annual land-use change emissions for the 2010 to 2020 period were much lower than their annual values over the last 50 years and are assumed to remain constant at their 2010 to 2020 period value over the entire model period. In order to return to pre-industrial atmospheric conditions, the historic atmospheric sink needs to be sequestered. To do so, the carbon sequestration amount assigned to reduce the historic atmospheric sink, is annually increased with a small fraction until the atmospheric sink is empty. Using these inputs, the C-sequestration requirements per dollar global consumer spending are calculated. This in turn allows calculation (based on the product price) of the C-sequestration requirements for each participating product sold to a participating end-user consumer. During product payment, the C-sequestration requirements are purchased immediately (electronically) by the end-user consumer using an electronic voucher (E-voucher) provided by the seller. E-vouchers are not issued for non-participating product or to non-participating end-user consumers. The model continues to increase the annual C-sequestration capacity, until the atmospheric sink is eliminated for case A. From that year onwards, no additional DACCS facilities are added. The existing C-sequestration capacity is used until the entire atmospheric sink and the fraction of the oceanic sink for each ocean venting scenario are eliminated for case B. The Excel model (39) allows calculation of the required C-sequestration capacity, to reach pre-industrial atmospheric conditions, for target years between 5 and 100 for case B.

7.2. Levelized Costs of DAC and DACCS

Direct air capture (DAC) processes can be categorized using low (LT) or high temperatures (HT). The LT processes (< 100 °C) have significant lower current DAC costs (46). Fasihi *et al.* (2019) (46) define conservative and base scenarios for DAC cost reduction over time. The scenarios are defined around the extent to which action is taken to meet the 2015 Paris Accord and based on DAC learning rates. The conservative scenario represents a 50% implementation of the DAC capacity required to meet the Paris Accord objectives (due to delays) and a 10% DAC learning rate. The base scenario represents a 100% on time and effective implementation and a DAC learning rate of 15%, which better matches the type of technological development used for DAC. I assume that over time the LT processes will dominate and will only use costs for LT DAC processes for the model calculations (71). Both for the conservative and base scenario electrical power and process heat are needed, where the process heat adds significant costs to the process. However, for the first generations of DAC plants, large amounts of process heat can be made available free (or almost free) when DAC plants are located next to other plants producing such waste heat, while the last generations of DAC plants could be located next to plants utilizing DAC CO₂ for the production of synthetic fuels (methanol or methane) also generating sufficient amounts of waste heat (46). With decreasing energy demands of DAC, the waste heat from water electrolyzer and methanation systems or high lift or high temperature heat pumps (68, 69, 70) could provide all heat required by LT DAC processes by 2030 and onwards (46, 47). DAC costs by Fasihi *et al.* 2019 (47) are shown in table 6 and figure 7.1. Due to their lower cost, likely only LT processes will be

Year	HT DAC - CS [€/tCO ₂]	HT DAC - BS [€/tCO ₂]	LT DAC - CS [€/tCO ₂]	LT DAC - BS [€/tCO ₂]	LT DAC CS - FH [€/tCO ₂]	LT DAC - BS - FH [€/tCO ₂]
2020	268	268	222	222	133	133
2030	133	111	105	84	60	39
2040	91	72	69	53	40	24
2050	71	54	54	38	32	16

Table 6: Conservative and base scenarios DAC costs estimates for high (HT) and low temperature (LT) DAC with or without free heat (FH) availability. Data as presented by Fasihi *et al.* 2019 (47). These costs do not include permanent CO₂ storage, CO₂ transportation to the storage site or a profit margin for DAC producers.

used at very large scales. Within these LT processes, the amine-based systems using temperature swing processes are likely to be optimized to require the smallest possible temperature lifts, such that heat can be provided by heat pumps at high COP. By selecting different R-groups, a variety of amine systems will likely be developed, each

suitable for different climates. Of the LT DAC cost profiles in table 6 only the highest (LT DAC CS) and lowest cost options (LT DAC BS – FH) will be used in the model. For the low temperature DAC conservative scenario (LT DAC CS), costs drop from 222 €/tCO₂ in 2020 to 54 €/tCO₂ in 2050. For the low temperature base scenario using free heat (LT DAC BS – FH) costs drop from 133 €/tCO₂ in 2020 to 16 €/tCO₂ in 2050. In both cases permanent underground CO₂ storage costs need to be added at € 10/tCO₂ (46, 50) and are assumed to be constant over the model period. For the conservative case the costs of CO₂ transportation will be added (at € 9/tCO₂), while for the FH case the DAC plants is assumed to be sighted directly above its permanent storage reservoir. The LT DAC BS – FH cost profile would also represent the lower half of the long-term costs range (11 - 38 €/tCO₂) (46, 48, 49) anticipated for the Global Thermostat process, but in that case without the requirement for free process heat (LT DAC BS – GT). The same exchange rate of 1.33 US \$/€ is used for the model as used by Fasihi *et al.* 2019 (46).

Figure 7.1. Levelized costs of DAC (LCOD) for low temperature (LT) processes under conservative scenario (CS), conservative scenario with free heat (CS – FH), base scenario (BS) and base scenario with free heat (BS - FH) as defined and calculated by Fasihi *et al.* 2019 (46). Only the LT conservative scenario (CS) and the LT base scenario with free heat (BS – FH) are used in our model. Note that these costs represent the DAC costs only and exclude cost of transport, underground storage and profit (77).

7.3. Default Input Variables and Constants

Default input values for the DACCS C-sequestration model are listed in table 7.1. For simplicity, the world population was kept constant at 8 billion over the model period. However, the world population is expected to rise to 9.8 billion in 2050 (43). The next 40 - 60 years represent the most critical C-sequestration period. World GDP data of 101 billion US \$ (42) and world consumer spending data of 71.5 billion US \$ (44) originate from the World Bank and are used to calculate the global consumer spending at 55% (50) of world GDP. For the (real) world GDP growth rate, the current IMF growth rate (45) is assumed to continue over the model period (2.9% real growth rounded up to 3 %). The fossil emissions from additional capacity are assumed to continue at current rates and phase out over a 20-year period. Each additional capacity facility has a default operational period of 30 years. Annual CO₂ fluxes and sink amounts are derived from Friedlingstein *et al.* 2021 (20). For the default scenario the assumption is made that the entire ocean sink would be accessible for C-sequestration. While a large number of model variables are used, the DACCS system capacity increase under IMACS is primarily a function of the eight yellow highlighted IMACS variables listed in table 7.1. The model results are converged, when the set target period to reach atmospheric CO₂ conditions for case B are met. The main results are the number of 1 MtCO₂/y sequestration

Input Variables	Values	Units
World population 2022 (assumed constant over model period)	8.00E+09	[p]
World GDP at year zero (= 2022)	1.01E+14	[\$/y]
World consumer spending as % of world GDP	55%	[%]
Average annual world GDP growth	3.0%	[%/y]
Fossil emission from additional capacity (annual increase 2023)	5.000E+08	[tCO ₂ /y]
Phase-out period for construction of additional capacity fossil fuel emission sources	20	[y]
Operational period for additional capacity fossil fuel emission sources	30	[y]
Annual Fossil CO ₂ emissions 2022	10.48	[GtC/y]
Annual Land-Use change CO ₂ emissions 2022	0.944	[GtC/y]
Annual flux to Land and Cement sinks 2022	3.291	[GtC/y]
Annual flux to ocean sinks 2022	3.161	[GtC/y]
Historic atmospheric CO ₂ accumulation 2022	298.95	[GtC]
Historic CO ₂ accumulation in atmospheric and ocean sinks 2022	483.8	[GtC]
Percentage of ocean sink vented until case B conditions are met	30%	%
Period to 100% customer participation	20	[y]
Period to 100% product participation	20	[y]
Period for reduction of current C-Emissions to zero	20	[y]
Start historic CO ₂ sequestration in year	10	[y]
Convergence parameter P _C	0.33031%	[%/y]
Atmospheric CO ₂ concentration in 2022	418	ppm
Atmospheric CO ₂ concentration in 1750	278	ppm
Target sequestration period to reach year 1750 atmospheric conditions for case B.	40	[y]
Permanent underground CO ₂ storage costs	13.30	[\$/tCO ₂]
CO ₂ transportation costs	11.97	[\$/tCO ₂]
DAC profit margin	20%	
Adjustment factor to reach "average" annual atmospheric CO ₂ concentration	0.50000	[]
Energy cost savings for 100% transition to roof PV solar, HSHPs and E-cars	3.62%	%GDP
ACGR needed to reach year 1750 conditions for Case A	126.0%	
Use CAGR instead of CO ₂ emission based DACCS capacity calculations (1 = Yes)	0	

Table 7.1: Default input values for IMACS C-sequestration model (77, 78). Yellow fields indicate variables changed during evaluations. The pink field reflects the convergence parameter that is changed (using goal seek) to reach the set target C-sequestration period for case B. The green fields represent the flag (0 or 1) to use CAGR instead of CO₂ emission based DACCS capacity calculations and the CAGR percentage needed to reach the set target sequestration period for case B.

facilities needed to meet the target conditions, atmospheric CO₂ concentration profiles, the periods needed to reach peak CO₂ and carbon neutrality for cases A and B, and the period to reach net ocean venting and all associated costs aspects for the conservative and base DACCS cost scenarios for Case B. The Convergence Parameter P_C is used to adjust the annual fraction of the remaining historical C-emission sink that is added to the annual amount to be sequestered, in order to meet the target period for reaching pre-industrial conditions for Case B. With respect to IMACS induced purchases, the global costs paid for DACCS are limited by the global supply of sequestered CO₂ and distributed over all participating retailers. For retailers, these costs as percentage of sales, would go up with higher DACCS capacity and go down with increasing numbers of participating retailers. Retailer participation is likely to follow consumer participation. Consumer participation can be increased by good marketing. The model allows a delay of the requirement to start sequestration of “historic” CO₂ emissions. A 40-year period was chosen as the default for reaching pre-industrial atmospheric conditions for case B, as it appeared to be a challenging, but potentially feasible and cost-effective period.

7.4. Calculation of Anthropogenic Land Absorption and Ocean Absorption and Vent Fluxes

The anthropogenic land and ocean CO₂ absorption fluxes are calculated as linear trendlines in figures 6.3A and 6.4B. To optimize model convergence and minimize residual error, the constants used for slope and intercept were further refined to create zero value fluxes once pre-industrial atmospheric conditions are reached (at 278 ppm CO₂). These constants are listed in table 7.1 under “Linear Trendline Slopes and Constants”. The anthropogenic ocean vent flux is calculated using the annual mass balance assuming removal of equal fractions of CO₂ from both atmospheric and ocean sinks. Both the anthropogenic absorption and vent fluxes are calculated. The oceanic carbon cycle fluxes between land and ocean are large. Under pre-industrial atmospheric conditions, the CO₂ absorption flux from atmosphere to ocean A_{O,P} and the vent flux from ocean to atmosphere E_{O,P} were the same in magnitude (about 80 GtC/y), resulting in a zero net difference (A_{O,Δ,1750} = 0). This changed with increasing atmospheric CO₂ levels

leading to an increase of the ocean absorption flux. I define the anthropogenic ocean absorption flux $A_{O,\Delta,y}$ as the amount of CO₂ absorbed in addition to the pre-industrial oceanic absorption flux $A_{O,P}$ between land and ocean.

$$A_{O,\Delta,y} = A_{O,A,y} - A_{O,P} \qquad A_{O,\Delta,2022} = 83 - 80 = 3 \text{ GtC/y}$$

with $A_{O,\Delta,y}$	= anthropogenic ocean absorption flux in year y	[GtCO ₂ /y]
with $A_{O,A,y}$	= ocean absorption flux in year y	[GtCO ₂ /y]
with $A_{O,P}$	= pre-industrial oceanic absorption flux (year 1750)	[GtCO ₂ /y]

The same applies to ocean vent fluxes. Anthropogenic vent fluxes are created when anthropogenic CO₂ sequestration fluxes are larger than anthropogenic CO₂ emissions fluxes, resulting in atmospheric CO₂ concentrations at the ocean surface below the equilibrium concentration for the surface water layer. I define the anthropogenic ocean vent flux $E_{O,\Delta,y}$ as the amount of CO₂ vented in addition to the pre-industrial oceanic vent flux $E_{O,P}$ between land and ocean (73).

$$E_{O,\Delta,y} = E_{O,A,y} - E_{O,P} \qquad E_{O,\Delta,2022} = \sim 0 \text{ GtC/y}$$

with $A_{O,\Delta,y}$	= anthropogenic ocean vent flux in year y	[GtCO ₂ /y]
with $E_{O,A,y}$	= ocean vent flux in year y	[GtCO ₂ /y]
with $E_{O,P}$	= pre-industrial oceanic vent flux (year 1750) with $E_{O,P} = A_{O,P}$	[GtCO ₂ /y]

In the model under case B, the assumption is made that the removal of CO₂ using DACCS from the “top ocean layer” is as easy as it would be to remove it from a “parallel” atmosphere. For the model calculations, the anthropogenic ocean vent flux in year y is calculated as its proportion to the overall sink amount to be removed:

$$E_{O,\Delta,y} = A_{D,y} * S_{O,y-1} / (S_{O,y-1} + S_{A,y-1})$$

with $A_{D,y}$	= DACCS flux in year y	[GtCO ₂ /y]
with $S_{O,y-1}$	= ocean sink in year y-1 (amount accessible for venting)	[GtCO ₂]
with $S_{A,y-1}$	= atmospheric sink in year y-1	[GtCO ₂]

The net ocean absorption or vent flux F_O is calculated as the difference of the anthropogenic ocean absorption and vent fluxes:

$$F_O = A_{O,\Delta,y} - E_{O,\Delta,y} = (A_{O,A,y} - A_{O,P}) - (E_{O,A,y} - E_{O,P}) = A_{O,A,y} - E_{O,A,y} \quad [\text{GtCO}_2/\text{y}]$$

In all cases “period totals” reflect only the amounts emitted or absorbed over the model period needed to reach pre-industrial atmospheric conditions for the specific case. Note that both absorption and vent fluxes are defined as “positive” fluxes, such that deduction leads to a much smaller or zero net flux.

7.5. Cost Savings of Living Carbon Neutral

A future sustainable society needs to sequester more CO₂ than it emits and do so for decades in order to reduce atmospheric CO₂ concentrations to levels where remaining effects of global warming no longer threaten biodiversity. The costs of energy for a future carbon negative society are anticipated to be roughly the same or higher compared to current costs, with PV solar and wind as the main renewable energy (RE) sources and H₂ replacing natural gas where no other options are available (39). Overall, electric and natural gas utilities will need to transition to their future sustainable renewable equivalent. Due to the much lower costs, energy systems of building will transition from 100% relying of electric and natural gas utilities to almost fully relying on roof mounted PV solar, with partial seasonal storage of energy. Electric power generating and natural gas producing and distribution companies will need to transition from providing base load electricity and natural gas, to providing medium (days, weeks) and seasonal term electricity storage, using batteries, H₂ electrolyzers, pressurized H₂ storage and H₂ fuel cell systems. Electric power generating companies will need to transition from a price structure where large users pay the lowest electricity distribution costs to one where the most sustainable producers (roof solar systems) pay the lowest (on no) electricity distribution costs, since only under those conditions the costs for the transition to a sustainable RE based society can be paid out of the savings made from rooftop PV solar systems (39).

While RE electricity is already cheaper than fossil fuel-based electricity, the investments electric utilities need to make (for H₂ electrolyzers, H₂ fuel cells and major distribution network upgrades) combined with the cost of sunk investment (fossil power plants) make it unlikely that the price of electricity for the end-users will be lower than today. While the prices of H₂ (in \$/kWh) are touted to be equivalent or lower than for today's natural gas, these are still future projections and are thus uncertain (50). No such uncertainties apply to savings made for user owned roof PV solar systems, heat pumps and electric cars. The combination of electricity generation using roof mounted South facing PV solar, heating and cooling using ground source heat pumps (GSHP) and electric driving save 80% of the costs otherwise paid for the use of electric utilities, natural gas heating and fossil fuel cars. The potential societal cost savings for using south facing roof PV solar, GSHP, electric driving, High Lift Very and High Temperature Heat Pumps were estimated at 3.62% of GDP for each year with 100% conversion to such energy systems (39). Note that these savings are labeled “potential” since they would require all buildings to have 100% south facing roofs and would require installation of PV solar systems over the full roof area of all buildings (residential, commercial and industrial). For east – west facing roofs or the use of air source heat pumps (ASHP), the estimated savings would be respectively 22% and less 24% less or in combination 43% less.

7.6. Calculation of Different Atmospheric CO₂ Concentrations for Cases A and B

The results for cases A and B are calculated in the same spreadsheet using the same number of installed DACCS facilities. The spreadsheet first calculates the C-sequestration capacity needed to reach pre-industrial conditions for Case A (removing only the atmospheric sink). Once pre-industrial atmospheric conditions are reached for Case A, the existing DACCS capacity is used to reach pre-industrial atmospheric conditions for Case B. This partial “front-end loading” of installed DACCS installations leads to a longer usage period of the average DACCS installation, corresponding to a higher equipment utilization. Since for Case B, a fraction of the ocean CO₂ sink amount needs to be sequestered in addition to case A, the resulting atmospheric CO₂ concentration profiles versus time are different for cases A and B.

8. C-Sequestration Model Results

8.1. Variation of Period to Reverse Climate Change

Results under default input conditions are listed in table 8.1. Under default conditions the entire ocean sink is stored in the top ocean layer and assumed to vent to the atmosphere prior to reaching pre-industrial atmospheric conditions for case B. The default results show that a total of 61,157 DACCS facilities each with a 1 million-ton CO₂ sequestration capacity per year (1 MtCO₂/y) are needed to return to pre-industrial atmospheric conditions. Under those conditions, global carbon neutrality (peak atmospheric CO₂) is reached in year 8, net ocean venting starts in year 23 (Case B), while pre-industrial atmospheric conditions for Case A are reached in year 35 and in year 40 for Case B. DACCS costs under the conservative scenario differ strongly from the base scenario. For the conservative and base DACCS cost scenarios, the peak year retailer DACCS costs are respectively 4.9 and 1.8% of revenues (table 8.1). Since of all costs, the retailer DACCS costs are the highest, I will focus on these costs.

Increasing the C-sequestration period to 50 years reduces the number of 1 mill tCO₂/year DACCS plants to 40,416 and reduces the peak year retailer DACCS costs for the conservative and base scenarios to respectively 3.0 and 1.1% of revenues (table 8.2), dropping further to respectively 2.2 and 0.9% of revenues for a 60-year sequestration period (table 8.3). In the 50 and 60-year cases, these costs are well below the expected 3.62% of GDP savings for each year with 100% conversion to renewable energy systems. Comparing the average C-sequestration costs as percentage of GDP over the three C-sequestration periods, the costs for the 40, 50 and 60-year periods are respectively 0.7 – 1.8%, 0.4 – 1.2% and 0.3 – 0.9% of GDP for the base and conservative DACCS cost scenarios. Comparing the average C-sequestration costs as percentage of GDP over a century, the costs for the 40, 50 and 60-year periods are respectively 0.3 – 0.7%, 0.2 – 0.6% and 0.2 – 0.5% of GDP for the base and conservative DACCS cost scenarios. The conservative and base case DACCS cost scenarios are compared in figure 8.1, where the ratio of cumulative

Calculation Results	Values	Units	
Total number of 1 MtCO ₂ /y C-sequestration plants needed	61,157	[]	
Peak atmospheric CO ₂ concentration for case A	428.3	[ppm CO ₂]	
Peak atmospheric CO ₂ concentration for case B	428.5	[ppm CO ₂]	
Atmospheric CO ₂ concentration reached in last main DACS year for case A	274.8	[ppm CO ₂]	
Atmospheric CO ₂ concentration reached in last Main DACS year for case B	270.7	[ppm CO ₂]	
Period to peak atmospheric CO ₂ concentration Case A (carbon neutrality)	8	[y]	
Period to peak atmospheric CO ₂ concentration Case B (carbon neutrality)	8	[y]	
First year of net ocean venting (Case B)	23	[y]	
Shortest period to pre-industrial atmospheric conditions (= Case A)	35.5	[y]	
Longest period to pre-industrial atmospheric conditions (= Case B)	40.0	[y]	
Total of remaining fossil and Land-use change emissions over sequestration period	5.09E+11	[tCO ₂]	
Total of New Emissions (from additional capacity in next 100 years)	1.43E+11	[tCO ₂]	
Total land sink absorption over DACCS period for case A	3.72E+11	[tCO ₂]	
Total land sink absorption over DACCS period for case B	4.01E+11	[tCO ₂]	
Additional ocean sink absorption over DACCS period for case A	3.11E+11	[tCO ₂]	
Additional ocean sink absorption over DACCS period for case B	3.35E+11	[tCO ₂]	
Peak of anthropogenic ocean vent flux Case B (not mass transfer limited)	-1.59E+10	[tCO ₂ /y]	
CO2 Sequestration Costs and Payments for Scenarios:	Conservative	Base	
Total of all DACCS payments	1.64E+14	5.91E+13	[\$]
Average cost of DACCS	119.76	43.03	[\$/tCO ₂]
Peak C-sequestration costs as % of GDP over 100-year period	2.68%	0.97%	[%]
Peak seller E-voucher costs as % of sale	4.87%	1.77%	[%]
Peak Carbon Neutral seller's E-voucher costs as % of sale	4.39%	1.58%	[%]
Average C-sequestration costs as % of GDP over sequestration period	1.78%	0.65%	[%]
Average C-sequestration costs as % of GDP over 100-year period	0.73%	0.26%	[%]
Ratio cumulative energy cost savings / DACCS costs over 100-year period	4.5	12.4	[-]

Table 8.1: IMACS C-sequestration model outputs for default input values (40-year sequestration period). (72, 74, 77, 78, 80).

Calculation Results	Values	Units	
Total number of 1 MtCO ₂ /y C-sequestration plants needed	40,416	[]	
Peak atmospheric CO ₂ concentration for case A	428.3	[ppm CO ₂]	
Peak atmospheric CO ₂ concentration for case B	428.5	[ppm CO ₂]	
Atmospheric CO ₂ concentration reached in last main DACS year for case A	274.6	[ppm CO ₂]	
Atmospheric CO ₂ concentration reached in last Main DACS year for case B	273.3	[ppm CO ₂]	
Period to peak atmospheric CO ₂ concentration Case A (carbon neutrality)	8	[y]	
Period to peak atmospheric CO ₂ concentration Case B (carbon neutrality)	8	[y]	
First year of net ocean venting (Case B)	28	[y]	
Shortest period to pre-industrial atmospheric conditions (= Case A)	43.3	[y]	
Longest period to pre-industrial atmospheric conditions (= Case B)	50.0	[y]	
Total of remaining fossil and Land-use change emissions over sequestration period	5.43E+11	[tCO ₂]	
Total of New Emissions (from additional capacity in next 100 years)	1.43E+11	[tCO ₂]	
Total land sink absorption over DACCS period for case A	4.22E+11	[tCO ₂]	
Total land sink absorption over DACCS period for case B	4.61E+11	[tCO ₂]	
Additional ocean sink absorption over DACCS period for case A	3.53E+11	[tCO ₂]	
Additional ocean sink absorption over DACCS period for case B	3.85E+11	[tCO ₂]	
Peak of anthropogenic ocean vent flux Case B (not mass transfer limited)	-1.22E+10	[tCO ₂ /y]	
CO2 Sequestration Costs and Payments for Scenarios:	Conservative	Base	
Total of all DACCS payments	1.53E+14	5.46E+13	[\$]
Average cost of DACCS	118.28	42.25	[\$/tCO ₂]
Peak C-sequestration costs as % of GDP over 100-year period	1.66%	0.61%	[%]
Peak seller E-voucher costs as % of sale	3.01%	1.10%	[%]
Peak Carbon Neutral seller's E-voucher costs as % of sale	2.56%	0.91%	[%]
Average C-sequestration costs as % of GDP over sequestration period	1.18%	0.43%	[%]
Average C-sequestration costs as % of GDP over 100-year period	0.60%	0.22%	[%]
Ratio cumulative energy cost savings / DACCS costs over 100-year period	5.4	15.0	[-]

Table 8.2: IMACS C-sequestration model outputs for 50-year sequestration period using otherwise default input values.

cost savings over cumulative DACCS costs paid is shown (78). Even under the conservative DACCS price scenario and during the highest DACCS production period (20 – 40 years after start), the cumulative savings remain higher than the cumulative costs. During the period 40 – 100-year after start, the savings accumulate and the ratios reach 6 – 17 for respectively the conservative and base DACCS costs scenarios over a century. This does not include any other cost savings or damage prevented related to biodiversity, flooding, severe storms, or loss of human life, which are estimated to be orders of magnitude higher (9).

	Values	Units
Calculation Results		
Total number of 1 MtCO ₂ /y C-sequestration plants needed	29,603	[-]
Peak atmospheric CO ₂ concentration for case A	428.3	[ppm CO ₂]
Peak atmospheric CO ₂ concentration for case B	428.5	[ppm CO ₂]
Atmospheric CO ₂ concentration reached in last main DACS year for case A	276.8	[ppm CO ₂]
Atmospheric CO ₂ concentration reached in last Main DACS year for case B	274.7	[ppm CO ₂]
Period to peak atmospheric CO ₂ concentration Case A (carbon neutrality)	8	[y]
Period to peak atmospheric CO ₂ concentration Case B (carbon neutrality)	8	[y]
First year of net ocean venting (Case B)	33	[y]
Shortest period to pre-industrial atmospheric conditions (= Case A)	50.6	[y]
Longest period to pre-industrial atmospheric conditions (= Case B)	60.0	[y]
Total of remaining fossil and Land-use change emissions over sequestration period	5.78E+11	[tCO ₂]
Total of New Emissions (from additional capacity in next 100 years)	1.43E+11	[tCO ₂]
Total land sink absorption over DACCS period for case A	4.65E+11	[tCO ₂]
Total land sink absorption over DACCS period for case B	5.13E+11	[tCO ₂]
Additional ocean sink absorption over DACCS period for case A	3.89E+11	[tCO ₂]
Additional ocean sink absorption over DACCS period for case B	4.29E+11	[tCO ₂]
Peak of anthropogenic ocean vent flux Case B (not mass transfer limited)	-1.01E+10	[tCO ₂ /y]
CO2 Sequestration Costs and Payments for Scenarios:		
	Conservative	Base
Total of all DACCS payments	1.45E+14	5.18E+13
Average cost of DACCS	117.69	41.94
Peak C-sequestration costs as % of GDP over 100-year period	1.21%	0.47%
Peak seller E-voucher costs as % of sale	2.20%	0.85%
Peak Carbon Neutral seller's E-voucher costs as % of sale	1.70%	0.61%
Average C-sequestration costs as % of GDP over sequestration period	0.85%	0.31%
Average C-sequestration costs as % of GDP over 100-year period	0.52%	0.19%
Ratio cumulative energy cost savings / DACCS costs over 100-year period	6.3	17.4

Table 8.3: IMACS C-sequestration model results for 60-year sequestration period using otherwise default input values.

Figure 8.1. Ratio of potential cumulative societal energy savings over cumulative societal DACCS costs paid for a 40-year (Case B) global warming reversal period and a 30% fraction of ocean sink accessible for sequestration ($F_{OSA} = 30\%$). The energy savings arise from user owned roof PV solar, the use of GSHPs and E-cars, compared to the use of natural gas heating systems, classic AC cooling systems using utility provided natural gas and electricity and fossil fuel cars. The assumption is made that electricity prices remain at current levels and H₂ prices drop to their current natural gas values expressed in dollar per kWh.

For US businesses, DACCS costs are already tax deductible as business expenses. However, based on the potentially huge societal savings it would be cost effective to make the fraction of DACCS costs reflecting sequestration of historic CO₂ emission tax refundable. This would remove all financial burdens from retailers and other supply chain actors and likely accelerate business participation, while maintaining cost savings incentives to become carbon neutral. The societal costs savings are many times larger than the tax receipts missed.

8.2. Percentage of Anthropogenic CO₂ Vented from Oceans

CO₂ absorption and venting take place at the ocean's surface. CO₂ absorbed from the atmosphere is mixed into the mixed layer. A fraction of the mixed layer is annually mixing into deeper layers and vice versa. The water layer still containing significant amounts of CO₂ extends to water much deeper than the mixed layer (50). I refer to this layer as the “top” ocean layer. The CO₂ of top ocean layer water, mixed into the deep ocean is essentially no longer accessible for venting, since the probability that this CO₂ finds its way back to the surface is very small. Deep ocean water rising to the surface can have high CO₂ concentrations in the form of calcium carbonate (50). Water rising up to the surface with high CO₂ concentrations would increase the ocean sink CO₂ fraction available for venting at sufficiently low atmospheric CO₂ concentrations. The amount of CO₂ in the top ocean layer is thus strongly dependent on vertical ocean mixing. To keep it simple, I will assume four different scenarios with each different fractions (F_{OSA}) of the total ocean carbon sink that could be vented and sequestered using DACCS. The four scenarios assume 100%, 50%, 30% or 10% of the total ocean sink CO₂ to be present in the top ocean water layer. In each case these fractions are assumed be vented and sequestered via DACCS. Otherwise, default model conditions are used. A selection of model inputs and outputs are combined in table 8.4, while a selection of results is shown in figures 8.2 and 8.3. The “Peak anthropogenic ocean vent flux for Case B (not mass transfer limited)” is about 10 times smaller under the 10% scenario compared to the 100% scenario. The number of C-sequestration plants needed drops to almost half under the 10% scenario compared to the 100% scenario. The “Peak Carbon Neutral Seller's E-voucher costs as % of sale” drop to less than half for the 10% scenario compared to the 100% scenario. Based on literature values (80), the percentage of the ocean CO₂ sink that remains in the top ocean layer is likely in the 30% range (50). For this case, 61,157 DACCS plants (1 MtCO₂/y each) would need to be built in 36 years in order to reverse global warming in 40 years. This case corresponds with “Peak Carbon Neutral Seller's E-voucher costs as % of sale” of 4.9 and 1.8% for respectively the conservative and base DACCS cost scenarios (table 8.4, figure 8.3) (85).

Figure 8.2: The number of C-sequestration plants needed increases drastically with the fraction of the ocean sink vented during the period until pre-industrial atmospheric condition are reached. Data corresponding with table 8.4. (75, 85).

The ratio of cumulative energy cost savings over cumulative DACCS payments over the 100-year period following model year zero, for the four F_{OSA} percentages and for the conservative and base DACCS cost scenarios, rise from 3 to 14. Hence, even under the least favorable conditions, the cumulative societal energy savings made are about 4 times larger than the cumulative DACCS costs. The C-sequestration model used has no functionality to estimate the bi-directional mass transport rates between the top layer and deeper ocean layer and neither can it calculate the fraction of the total ocean sink that is expected to vent to the atmosphere during the period until pre-industrial atmospheric conditions are reached. This will need to be calculated by others. However, with respect to the period needed to reach pre-industrial atmospheric conditions, the shortest and longest periods are represented by cases A and B. The resulting uncertainty for the worst scenario ($F_{OSA} = 100\%$) is 10 years which reduces to about 2 years for the most favorable scenario ($F_{OSA} = 10\%$).

Input Data (selection of larger set)	Anthropogenic CO2 sink fraction in top of ocean at start of model year 0									
Anthropogenic CO2 sink fraction remaining in top of ocean in model year 0	100%	100%	50%	50%	30%	30%	10%	10%		
Calculation Results (selection of larger set)	Conservative	Base	Conservative	Base	Conservative	Base	Conservative	Base		
Total number of 1 MtCO ₂ /y C-sequestration plants needed		93,558		71,061		61,157		50,632		[]
Peak atmospheric CO ₂ concentration for case A		428		428		428		428		[ppm CO ₂]
Peak atmospheric CO ₂ concentration for case B		429		429		429		428		[ppm CO ₂]
Period to peak atmospheric CO ₂ concentration Case A (carbon neutrality)		8.0		8.0		8.0		8.0		[y]
Period to peak atmospheric CO ₂ concentration Case B (carbon neutrality)		8		8		8		8		[y]
First year of net ocean venting (Case B)		16		19		23		31		[y]
Shortest period to pre-industrial atmospheric conditions (= Case A)		30		33		36		38		[y]
Longest period to pre-industrial atmospheric conditions (= Case B)		40		40		40		40		[y]
Peak of anthropogenic ocean vent flux Case B (not mass transfer limited)		5.0E+10		2.6E+10		1.6E+10		5.3E+09		[tCO ₂ /y]
Total of all DACCS payments	2.51E+14	9.01E+13	1.89E+14	6.79E+13	1.64E+14	5.91E+13	1.40E+14	5.03E+13		[\$]
Average cost of DACCS	119	43	119	43	120	43	120	43		[\$/tCO ₂]
Peak seller E-voucher costs as % of sale	7.87%	2.84%	5.67%	2.05%	4.87%	1.77%	4.10%	1.49%		[%]
Peak Carbon Neutral seller's E-voucher costs as % of sale	7.39%	2.66%	5.19%	1.87%	4.39%	1.58%	3.61%	1.30%		[%]
Peak C-sequestration costs as % of GDP over 100-year period	4.33%	1.56%	3.12%	1.13%	2.68%	0.97%	2.25%	0.82%		[%]
Average C-sequestration costs as % of GDP over sequestration period	2.68%	0.97%	2.03%	0.74%	1.78%	0.65%	1.53%	0.56%		[%]
Average C-sequestration costs as % of GDP over 100-year period	1.10%	0.40%	0.83%	0.30%	0.73%	0.26%	0.63%	0.23%		[%]
Ratio cumulative energy cost savings / DACCS costs over 100-year period	3.0	8.2	3.9	10.8	4.5	12.4	5.2	14.4		[-]

Table 8.4: Effects of the ocean sink fraction in the top ocean layer and treated as accessible for DACCS for 100%, 50%, 30% and 10%, using base case DACCS costs (75).

Societal Participation Scenario	Scenario I	Scenario I	Scenario II	Scenario II	Scenario III	Scenario III	Scenario IV	Scenario IV
DACCS Cost Scenario	Conserv.	Base	Conserv.	Base	Conserv.	Base	Conserv.	Base
Target period to reach year 1750 atmospheric conditions for case B [y]		40		60		80		100
Period to 100% customer % product participation [y]		20		30		40		50
Period for reduction of current C-Emissions to zero [y]		20		30		40		50
Phase-out period for new fossil fuel emission sources [y]		20		30		40		50
Operational period for anew fossil fuel emission sources [y]		20		30		40		50
Start historic CO ₂ sequestration in model year		10		15		20		25
Calculated Results (Selection of Larger Set)								
Total number of 1 MtCO ₂ /y C-sequestration plants needed		59,317		37,706		27,216		24,776
Peak atmospheric CO ₂ concentration for case A [ppm CO ₂]		428		434		441		447
Peak atmospheric CO ₂ concentration for case B [ppm CO ₂]		429		435		441		448
Period to peak atmospheric CO ₂ concentration Case A [y]		8		12		16		20
Period to peak atmospheric CO ₂ concentration Case B [y]		8		12		16		21
Period to first year of net ocean venting (Case B) [y]		23		36		49		62
Shortest period to pre-industrial atmospheric conditions (= Case A) [y]		35		52		68		84
Longest period to pre-industrial atmospheric conditions (= Case B) [y]		40		60		80		100
Peak of anthropogenic ocean vent flux Case B [tCO ₂ /y]		1.66E+10		1.21E+10		9.49E+09		7.72E+09
Average cost of DACCS [\$ /tCO ₂]	120	43.2	115	40.4	113	39.6	112	39.2
Peak seller E-voucher costs as % of sale	4.68%	1.72%	2.26%	0.79%	1.55%	0.54%	1.21%	0.42%
Peak Carbon Neutral seller's E-voucher costs as % of sale [%]	4.41%	1.59%	1.89%	0.66%	0.98%	0.34%	0.57%	0.20%
Peak C-sequestration costs as % of GDP over 100-year period [%]	2.58%	0.95%	1.25%	0.43%	0.85%	0.30%	0.67%	0.23%
Average C-sequestration costs as % of GDP over sequestration period	1.73%	0.63%	0.83%	0.29%	0.50%	0.18%	0.34%	0.12%
Average C-sequestration costs as % of GDP over 100-year period [%]	0.71%	0.26%	0.50%	0.18%	0.40%	0.14%	0.34%	0.12%
Ratio cumulative energy cost savings / DACCS costs over 100-year	4.6	12.7	6.1	17.2	7.2	20.5	8.0	22.7

Table 8.5: Results for model scenarios I, II, III and IV. For all cases the same 30% ocean sink accessibility and base DACCS cost scenario were used (75, 76).

Figure 8.3: CO₂ sequestration cost ((expressed as percentage of GDP) for a return to pre-industrial atmospheric conditions in 40 years, as function of the percentage of the total ocean sink vented during the CO₂ sequestration period (85).

8.3. Rate of Societal Participation

The model used is mostly driven by societal participation. This participation can be broken down in individual participation by end-user consumers, organizational participation and product (and service) participation. Theoretically, all types of participation are independent. However, under market conditions (and effective marketing), an increasing fraction of consumers motivated to buy IMACS participating products and services, will induce retailer and other supply chain actors to participate and provide such participating products and services. Organizational participation and product participation are also linked to the extent that an organization needs to participate in the IMACS in order for its products to participate. The percentage participation for products and services will increase with increasing DACCS capacity and reduce with increasing retailer participation, until they all reach 100%. However, when DACCS investors see that the entire capacity of each newly contracted DACCS plant is sold years ahead of plant completion, this will stimulate investors to build more DACCS plants. Participation is voluntary; individuals can join and start participation free of cost, while participation is expected to lead to customer savings. Good communication and effective marketing of the objectives would be required for IMACS implementation to be successful. For the model, individual and product participation (“*Environ. Voucher Products Available*”) are used and set to the same value for each calculation year. Organizations represent any group of people other than individual consumers and include businesses, governments and related organizations and NGOs. Participating organizations can supply goods and services to each other (B2B) and form a participating supply chain. Since individuals buy goods and services from retailers, the retailer to end-use-consumer interaction is the most important interaction. A value of “10% participating product” means that 10% of the retail product in the marketplace are available as IMACS participating product. Since this 10% can be made available by different percentages of organizational participation, no variable representing the organizational participation is needed. Both individual and product participation are calculated using a sigmoid function using their respective full (0 – 100%) transition periods. For both, 20-year periods are used by default. I will review four societal participation scenarios (I, II, III, IV), where scenario I reflects the highest level of societal participation and IV the lowest level of societal participation (see table 8.5). Seven variables are varied, while the rests are kept at default conditions. Results are shown in table 8.5. For reaching pre-industrial atmospheric conditions ranging from 40 to 100 years (for Case B), the model calculates peak atmospheric CO₂ concentration of 429 – 448 ppm to be reached in 8 - 21 years, with net ocean venting starting between 23 and 62 years and periods to pre-industrial atmospheric conditions for Case A ranging from 35 to 84 years, requiring 59,300 – 24,800 DACCS plants (1 MtCO₂/y each). For the conservative

DACCS cost scenario, and societal scenarios I to IV, the “Peak seller E-voucher costs as % of sale” drop from 4.7 to 1.2%, while the “Average C-sequestration costs as % of GDP over 100-year period” drop from 0.7 to 0.3% of GDP. The ratio of cumulative energy savings over the cumulative cost of DACCS rises from scenario I to IV from 4.6 to 8.0. For the base DACCS costs scenario) and societal scenarios I to IV, the “Peak seller E-voucher costs as % of sale” drop from 1.7 to 0.4%, while the “Average C-sequestration costs as % of GDP over 100-year period” drop from 0.26 to 0.12% of GDP. The ratio of cumulative energy savings over the cumulative cost of DACCS rises from scenario I to IV from 13 to 23. The increases happen since DACCS costs are at their lowest level for most of the CO₂ sequestered under scenario IV. This is a perverse result, since the economic damage and biodiversity losses are the highest for the scenario IV, but not included and thus not made visible in the calculations.

8.4. How Fast Can the DAC Industry Grow?

During the 2nd world war, US defense spending grew from 1.4 % of GDP in 1940 to over 37% of GDP in 1945. This compares to a compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of 92%.

$$\text{CAGR} = (\text{Final value} / \text{Initial Value})^{(1/\text{number of years})} - 1 = (37/1.4)^{0.2} - 1 = 92\%$$

Of course, WW2 represented unparalleled circumstances, where a government was willing to spend 37% of its GDP on its military. An important aspect allowing such growth rates, was the certainty that production capacity built would be close to fully utilized and products made would be paid for upon delivery, at least for a few years until the war would be over. The fraction of GDP that needs to be spent on DAC over the 40-year CO₂ sequestration period is 0.6 -1.4% of GDP and thus a factor 26 – 62 smaller than the US defense spending during WW2. A similar promise of DAC capacity utilization would take place under IMACS, where long term contracts with DAC producers would require delivery of the sequestered CO₂ in (say) 4 - 6 years. During these years, the sequestered CO₂ would already be sold (and money collected) to offset current and historic CO₂ emissions for products and services purchased, but the producers would only be paid for each ton of CO₂ actually sequestered and thus at product delivery. The moneys already collected and stored in bank accounts would provide confidence for the DAC industry that their capacity will indeed be fully utilized upon facility completion, reduce risk and stimulate additional investments. The question is whether the growth rates required to allow a reversal of global warming in about 40 years can be met? In addition to the demand-based calculations (participation based), the model also has functionality to calculate the DAC capacity using a constant annual growth rate. Two times and capacities are needed to evaluate the annual growth rate results; the year and capacity for the highest DAC growth year ($t_2 = 2037$) and the year and capacity for the highest DAC capacity year ($t_3 = 2057$). For the demand-based calculations, 2040 is the highest growth year, while 2058 has the highest capacity. Using the calculated DAC capacities (in sequestered tCO₂/y) for the model under default conditions for these two years, the capacity based CAGRs can be calculated (table 8.6). Even at the corresponding CAGR of 126%, the CAGR growth curve only catches up with the demand curve in model year 37. The production based CAGRs for periods 2023 to 2037 and for 2023 to 2057 are respectively 126 and 45% leading to global warming reversal period of respectively 40.0 and 45.5 years. The 45% CAGR also delays the start of ocean venting from model year 23 to 33. Using the anticipated average DAC prices for these years, the DAC revenues can be calculated, corresponding to revenue based CAGRs of respectively 112 and 40%. The production based CAGRs are about 13% higher for the three periods compared to the revenue based CAGRs. However, lower CAGR rates move the construction peak to later years, with not too much effect on the overall period for global warming reversal. For example; using a 63% CAGR moves the DACCS plant production peak from model year 15 to year 25, but only increases the period for global warming reversal by 1.5 years. Three marketing studies provide estimates of current and future DAC revenues for 2023 and 2030 – 2032. The estimated revenue values for 2023 were used to calculate the 2023 DAC capacity in tCO₂/y. The average revenue based CAGR of 37 – 62% (average 50%) would correspond to 42 – 70 (average 56%) production based CAGRs. These CAGR rates should be continued for 15 years, relaxed afterwards and be effective in global warming reversal. While these CAGRs are not high enough to reach a global warming reversal period of exactly 40 years, CAGR values of 45 – 65%, would lead to global warming reversal periods of respectively 45 – 41 years, requiring 14 –20% more DAC capacity, and would still drastically reduce biodiversity losses, loss of human lives and economic damage.

Modeled Results	Source	Year t_0	Year t_1	Year t_2	Year t_3
Model Year	Model	2023	2032	2037	2057
Modeled Capacity [tCO ₂ /y]	Model	2.02E+05	4.64E+08	1.80E+10	6.12E+10
Price sequestered CO ₂ [\$/tCO ₂]	Model	300.50	151.60	125.00	85.80
Modeled Revenues [\$/y]	Model	6.07E+07	7.03E+10	2.25E+12	5.25E+12
CAGR Period	Model		$t_0 - t_1$	$t_0 - t_2$	$t_0 - t_3$
Capacity based CAGR [%/y]	Model		136%	126%	45%
Revenue based CAGR [%/y]	Model		119%	112%	40%
Marketing Study Results	Study	Year t_0	Year t_1		
Model Year	1	2023	2032		
Model Year	2	2023	2030		
Model Year	3	2023	2032		
Estimated Revenues [\$/y]	1	6.07E+07	3.75E+09		
Estimated Revenues [\$/y]	2	6.20E+07	1.73E+09		
Estimated Revenues [\$/y]	3	1.50E+08	2.50E+09		
CAGR Period			$t_0 - t_1$		
Revenue based CAGR [%/y]	1		58%		
Revenue based CAGR [%/y]	2		61%		
Revenue based CAGR [%/y]	3		37%		
Average revenue based CAGR			50%		

Table 8.6: Upper section (A): Modeled using default conditions. The prices of sequestered CO₂ are calculated as the weighted average of high and low temperature process types, where the weight fraction of HT process drops to zero at the end of the price reduction period in year 2050 (81, Supplemental materials). The DAC production capacity (in red) is calculated using the average of the three revenue estimates listed in section B and multiplication by the price of sequestered CO₂. Lower section (B): Estimates of world-wide DAC revenues for 2023 and 2030 - 2032 and the corresponding CAGRs (82, 83, 84).

9. Growth of Participation Rates

The IMACS system is based on the concept of voluntary participation. While consumer participation sign-up is similar to signing-up for a bank account or credit card, there are no costs associated with the IMACS participation or the sign-up for individual customers. Retailers follow their customers; if large numbers of customers sign-up for participation, retailers will likely sign-up as well. Two-thirds of Americans (67%) prioritize developing alternative energy sources, like wind and solar, while 69% favor the US to become carbon neutral by 2050 (90). Another survey found that approximately six in ten Americans (59%) are either alarmed or concerned about climate change (91). The world's largest survey of public opinion on climate change, which covered 50 countries with over half of the world's population, found that 64% of people believe climate change is a global emergency (92). Based on this it should not be very hard to get enough people motivated to participate, especially when there are no costs and they know that it will force retailers (and eventually the entire supply chain) to become carbon neutral and otherwise sustainable. With good marketing it would not be impossible to see consumer participation increases of 10% per year or more until the concerned 2/3 fraction of the population has signed up. Maybe the question should be reversed; can the IMACS organization handle a 10% per year consumer participation growth? The model is flexible and would still reach a 40-year global warming reversal in 40-year at 2.5% per year consumer participation increase. Research suggests that more customers are willing to pay a premium price for sustainable products. Fortunately, under IMACS no premium prices are paid for any products; under the participation agreement, retailers must sell participating products for the same price to every customer independent of participation. Products are selected by the retailer for "participation" and are not necessarily more or less sustainable than non-participating others. The retailer can change product participation daily (as long as announced a day in advance). Participation growth is thus mostly a marketing challenge, something retailers and dedicated marketing firms do on a daily basis and is nothing to be concerned about. Employers favor participating employees, because they (likely) bring in less impacts for the products and services sold and thus cost less in neutralizing conservation to be applied. With enough customers and retailers participating, participation becomes the new normal. The sum of voucher costs paid (for the full spectrum of impacts types) will likely remain smaller than the sum of cumulative savings made from operating carbon neutral. The ongoing financing of the IMACS organization can very likely be paid out of the (low costs) software sold on massive scales to the world's retailers and their suppliers. The main hurdle to cross is the initial financing for patent prosecution and to set up the organization with non-profit and for-profit organizational elements.

10. Discussion and Conclusions

Feasibility. Global warming reversal appears feasible in a time frame of 40 - 60 years and can save large amounts of money due to savings in the costs or energy, minimize biodiversity losses, reduce the global loss of life and prevent economic damage. The upper end of the currently anticipated DACCS production-based growth rates of 42 - 70% for the 2023 – 2032 period would be sufficient for a global warming reversal in about 41 years, if continued for about 25 years at 63% CAGR. This requires a combination of a quick transition to RE in combination with an aggressive scale-up of DACCS plants. Continuation of such high growth rates may be possible when DACCS producers are offered a guaranteed 100% sales of their products and can make good profits (say 20%); conditions that can be offered under the IMACS business model. Irrespective of the exact period, the shortest period for climate change reversal is always preferred, since this will minimize both the irreversible biodiversity losses (extinctions) and the financial damage (50) resulting from climate change.

Costs and Savings. Over the 100-year model period and under default conditions, the average spending on CO₂ sequestration corresponds to 0.3 – 0.7% of GDP. Calculated over the 40-year period for Case B, this corresponds to 0.7 – 1.8% of GDP. These costs are one to two orders of magnitude smaller than the 30% to 70% loss of global income for the “business as usual” scenario of global warming (8, 50). For a 40-year global warming reversal period (and under otherwise default conditions), the costs of DACCS vary with the DACCS cost scenario (conservative versus base) and are low as percentage of GDP (0.73 – 0.26%). Initially, at very low customer and product participation, the seller’s costs of E-vouchers (to pay for CO₂ sequestration purchased by his participating customers) are low. For example, for 5% customer and 5% product participation, these costs represent 0.026 – 0.049% of sales (in year 3). However, these costs rise rapidly with rising participation. The (single year) peak costs for DACCS purchases for participating retailers are much higher (4.9 – 1.8% of revenues), but are smaller than their accumulated savings resulting from roof mounted PV solar, use of GSHPs and electric transportation. This is especially the case for early supply chain participants. However, even when such RE and more efficient use systems are installed and these savings are made, the DACCS payments made (through vouchers made available to participating customers buying participating products and services) are still additional costs. While these costs could be considered as the costs of doing business (at high customer participation rates non-participating retailers would lose most of their participating customers), DACCS payments made to sequester historic CO₂ emissions should be made tax refundable (not only tax deductible). The peak costs of DACCS as percentage of GDP are 1.0 – 2.7%. For a 40-year period (and under otherwise default conditions), the ratio of cumulative societal energy savings over cumulative DACCS costs are 5 – 12 over the 100-year period following the “starting” year. These energy savings only reflect the use of roof PV solar, excluding all costs avoided from doing less environmental damage, damage due to loss of ecosystem services and loss of income. It would thus be financially advantageous for governments to allow refunding of DACCS costs paid and allow their societies to collect the 5 -12 times higher savings (over a 100-year period) than the DACCS costs refunded. Such refunding should not apply to sequestration of “current” CO₂ emissions, since this would stop individuals and organizations to become carbon neutral themselves.

Tax Credits. In the, US tax credits up to \$ 180/tCO₂ sequestered are available under qualifying conditions (86). Such credits are close to the upper end of the 2018 cost estimate for one of the high temperature processes (9). For the conservative DACCS LT process scenario, the price of sequestered CO₂ (including CO₂ transportation) is expected to drop to \$ 180/tCO₂ by 2032 and for the base DACCS costs scenario LT (excl transportation) by 2028 (50). With current (2024) costs calculated to be between 166 – 305 (LT-FH base versus LT conservative with transportation, both including storage and 20% profits), US retailers would pay 0 – 125 \$/tCO₂ from qualifying DACCS producers (39). Once costs drop to or below \$ 180/tCO₂, the additional cost for US retailers and supply chain actors would drop essentially to nothing. However, no such tax credits for DAC are available in other countries and they could be lost in the US under different administrations. For that reason, tax credits were not applied in the calculation model.

Utility vs roof mounted PV solar. Prices of green H₂ are expected to drop to those of NG when expressed in \$/kWh. Compared to fossil fuel-based electricity, the cost of utility scale RE is already very low. While utility scale RE is expected to drop further, the incremental cost reductions will become insignificant to the end user, since most of the price of electricity reflects distribution costs and profits. However, due to the large investments needed by the electric utilities and the sunk costs of fossil power plants, consumer prices for electricity are not likely to drop; if anything, they are likely to increase. Alternatively, utility investments and losses may be subsidized by governments to prevent large increases in the price of electricity (either by tax write-off or by direct subsidies/handouts), leading to higher taxes. Consumers, businesses and the society as a whole can only benefit from the low cost of RE by installing (preferably South facing) PV solar on their own roofs, which they power their buildings at low costs, by using HPs (especially HSHPs) and by driving electric. The use of East -West facing PV solar or air source heat leads to significantly smaller savings (81). Without these savings, the changes required for a RE society will increase end-

user costs of energy and would reduce consumer spending power. The path along which RE future is implemented is thus critical.

Participation Rates. All purchases of sequestered carbon originate from participating customers buying participating product in participating retail stores. After this purchase, the customer leaves the store with a product net free of CO₂ emissions. Most customers aware of the issues related to Climate Change, will feel a satisfying feeling of individual contribution in fighting climate change, currently not available. Such customers will seek out more participating products at all participating retailers and can look up their improving individual sustainability and share these data with friends and family via social media. The vouchers used by the customers to buy the sequestered CO₂ are paid for by the retailers. Initially these costs are very low and a small fraction of their marketing costs. Retailers and sellers in general should treat these costs as “marketing costs”. At that time, the moneys paid for CO₂ sequestration may be their most effective marketing method when expressed as additional profits per dollar spending on CO₂ sequestration. The entire financing of the C-sequestration under the IMACS business model thus hinges on having sufficiently high rates of participation of both customers and retailers. Retailer and supply chain participation can never be too high, since the higher the seller participation, the lower the average seller DACCS costs (the costs to buy the available DACCS capacity are spread over more sellers). The same applies to customer participation but for different reasons; high customer participation will drive retailer and supply chain participation. At increasing retailer and customer participation, the product participation rate (set by the IMACS organization) will need to be reduced to match the daily available amounts of sequestered CO₂. With different retailer and customer participation rates, product participation rates will likely need to be set to different values in different countries or regions.

Reaching pre-industrial atmospheric conditions. Once pre-industrial global forcing conditions are reached, a fraction of the CO₂ sequestration facilities remain needed to further lower the atmospheric CO₂ concentrations to induce slightly “global cooling” conditions. These cooling conditions are needed to cool land masses and oceans to the 1750 mean temperatures. The desired degree of cooling and the corresponding atmospheric CO₂ concentration are unknown. However, at installed DACCS capacity and the annual atmospheric CO₂ reduction of 4.7 ppm/year it would not take long to reach the desired global forcing conditions. Once the desired global cooling conditions are reached, only a small fraction of the CO₂ sequestration facilities remain needed.

Forest venting. A small fraction of the installed peak CO₂ sequestration capacity is needed to capture CO₂ vented from forests. Per 2022, 68 % of all CO₂ was stored in atmospheric and oceans sinks while 31% was stored in the land sink (mostly forests). The fraction stored in forest will increase somewhat over the ~ 35-year period needed to reach pre-industrial atmospheric forcing conditions (estimate this new value). The forest venting will take place over a 200-year period. To sequester the CO₂ resulting from a constant forest venting rate over a 200-year period, 4 – 5 % of the CO₂ sequestration facilities would need to be maintained. In case of incomplete phasing out of fossil fuels, a larger fraction of these facilities must be maintained. Since no longer needed, most of the remaining facilities will need to shut down. The sunk investment cost for these facilities is assumed to be absorbed in the costs of the sequestered CO₂ during their period of use. The annual cost of CO₂ sequestration needed after reaching pre-industrial atmospheric forcing conditions are much lower than during earlier periods but are not included in any calculations.

Methane emissions are not included in the data reported by Friedlingstein et al. 2022 (20). Methane is oxidized in the atmosphere to CO₂ and water with a half-life of about 12 years (50). Annual methane emissions are equivalent to about 0.43 GtC/y (50) but are not included in the model. The 0.43 GtC/y equivalent methane emissions correspond to 4% of the average anthropogenic CO₂ emissions for the last decade. If we assume the methane emissions to remain constant over the 40-year DACCS period, this would correspond to 17.3 GtC. At an installed DACCS capacity of 61 GtC/y in year 40, the 17.3 GtC would require an additional 3.5 months of DACCS sequestration under default conditions.

IMACS business model. On May 8, 2024, The Guardian newspaper wrote the following: “*Hundreds of the world’s leading climate scientists expect global temperatures to rise to at least 2.5C (4.5F) above preindustrial levels this century, blasting past internationally agreed targets and causing catastrophic consequences for humanity and the planet, an exclusive Guardian survey has revealed. Almost 80% of the respondents, all from the authoritative Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC), foresee at least 2.5C of global heating, while almost half anticipate at least 3C (5.4F). Only 6% thought the internationally agreed 1.5C (2.7F) limit would be met. Many of the scientists envisage a “semi-dystopian” future, with famines, conflicts and mass migration, driven by heatwaves, wildfires, floods and storms of an intensity and frequency far beyond those that have already struck. Numerous experts [said they had been left feeling hopeless, infuriated and scared by the failure of governments to act](#) despite the clear scientific evidence provided.” The implementation of IMACS could drastically change this. Participation in IMACS is voluntary and cost-free for individuals. Using IMACS, the environmental impacts for products and services can be determined in a highly automated fashion and at low costs. Current and historic damaging impacts are calculated and assigned to participating products, services and individual labor. Under IMACS, in order for*

products and services to be calculated as “sustainable”, damaging impacts like greenhouse gas emissions must be eliminated or must be offset by CO₂ sequestered in permanent storage locations. Becoming carbon neutral saves large amounts of money compared to not doing so, even if carbon sequestration were free. Using the market costs of environmental conservation, the costs of environmental resource use, protection and restoration can be calculated. Under IMACS, the purchase of neutralizing amounts of sequestered CO₂ are paid during the products purchase with an electronic voucher provided by the retailer. This only applies to participating products sold by participating retailers to participating customers. The IMAC system puts consumers, retailers and organizations in general in charge of selling and buying incrementally less damaging and more sustainable products and services, while being awarded for their actions. This can happen independent of government action. For participating sellers, damaging impact and associated sustainabilities are accurately calculated (per store/seller’s location and daily adjusted) using automated and low costs systems. For non-participating competitor products, the impacts cannot be accurately calculated and are set to the statistic upper damage limit (2 -3 sigma) for each damage type for the product group (7). Sellers who start participation will almost always see large reductions in damaging product impacts and large increases in reported product sustainabilities. Participating sellers thus gain the moral high ground, while saving costs due to operating carbon neutral. This allows participating sellers to gain market share and outcompete their competition. After a while, this could become the new normal. This could dramatically accelerate the rate of change towards a sustainable world. To use an example; the Bison project DAC plant is expected to operate at 5 million tCO₂/y in 2030. Suppose Jan 1st 2025 is the start of the 1st practical model year and the Bison project would reach 5 million tCO₂/y on Jan 1, 2026 (model year 2), while no other DAC plants would be available. In that case, the demand for sequestered CO₂ would reach 5 mill tCO₂/y capacity on April 23th of that same year and the Bison project capacity would be fully assigned to IMACS consumers for the following 39 years. That would likely spark a boom in DAC plant construction. All technological aspects needed for humanity to become sustainable (or for this paper, carbon negative) are either already solved or in the process of optimization. Technical optimization is a process scientist and engineers know to do and they will be successful in doing so this time as well. The availability of IMACS reduces the problem from one of government inaction and consumer anxiety, powerlessness, and despair to one of empowerment, hope and agency. IMACS changes environmental issues from political to mere marketing challenges, a field in which humans are more capable. With good marketing campaigns, marketing firms should be able to convince consumers and retailers that participation in IMACS leads to large savings (both directly and as future lower or non-raised taxes) and increased incomes, while it protects the planet. Summarizing, by participating in IMACS, individuals and organizations can eliminate current CO₂ emissions, neutralize historic CO₂ emissions, save the planet, save money and improve their competitive position. IMACS, by assigning the costs of conservation (protection and restoration) to individuals and organizations responsible for the damage done, can effectively address and solve the classic “*tragedy of the commons*”.

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51. Note for future revisions: [Add reference](#)
52. Note for future revisions: [Add the figures or tables discussed here to a “Supplemental” document.](#)
53. Note for future revisions: With data for 2021 and 2022 now available it would be better to use the data for these additional years and do away with the extrapolations.
54. Note for future revisions: [Add a row with percentages to this table.](#)
55. Note for future revisions: [Add reference; possibly \(23\)](#)
56. Note for future revisions: While the Cement Carbonation Sink flux represents currently only 6% of the combined flux, with the developing world developing, the Cement Carbonation Sink flux will likely increase over the next half century, while the land flux will reduce for the reverse process. It is better to calculate the trendline for only the land sink flux and keep the Cement Carbonation Sink flux constant over the model period (next revision). The effects on the model are likely miniscule.
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58. Note for future revisions: Mention here that this laminar layer concept is theoretical and mixing to deeper does take place. List references.
59. Note for future revisions: Check the above six-line section to make sure it is sufficiently reworded from the original text.
60. Note for future revisions: Check the above two-line section to make sure it is sufficiently reworded from the original text.
61. Riebeck and Simmon, The Ocean’s Carbon Balance, NASA Earth Observatory 2008. [The Ocean’s Carbon Balance \(nasa.gov\)](#)
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[Impact of Anthropogenic CO₂ on the CaCO₃ System in the Oceans | Science](#)
64. Note for future revisions: I may want to reword this or otherwise explain this better.
65. Note for future revisions: Check this. This may need to be explained better.
66. Note for future revisions: I refer here to the figure with title “NET CO₂ FLUX TO AND FROM OCEAN, Case B”, shown in the calculation model. This is a “result” and the figure should be displayed in the section where results are discussed, but I should mention the figure number here.
67. Note for future revisions: Change text in figure of title to “No Anthropogenic Ocean venting”. Take out the “forest venting” arrow. Redo diagram, replace all handwritten text with typed text. Ask someone with skills to make a better figure!
68. Note for future revisions: In figure 6.6 change arrows to and from “Atmospheric Carbon Sink” to point or originate from the elliptic section labeled as “Atmospheric carbon Sink”, similar to figure 6.5. Change “High Fluxes” to “Reducing Fluxes to Ocean” and “Increasing Fluxes to Atmosphere”. Change “Reducing Net Flux” to “Reducing Flux to Land”. Change “Atmospheric Carbon Sink” to “Reducing Atmospheric CO₂ Concentration”. Keep title as is. [Note: Take out the “forest venting” arrow. Ask someone with skills to make a better figure!]
69. Zevenhoven, R., Khan, U., Haikarainen, C., Saeed, L., Tveit, T. M., & Saxén, H. (2020). Performance improvement of an industrial Stirling engine heat pump. *Proceedings of the ECOS*.
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71. Our Heat Pump, Airthium. [Airthium - Our Heat Pump](#). Captured 5/2/2024
72. Note for future revisions: One chart shown in the Excel model uses costs based on the conservative scenario while using base scenario data. Correct this. Later add both scenarios and show results in chart. Discuss both in text.
73. Note deleted.

74. Note for future revisions: This definition was based on the assumption that the oceanic vent flows did not change since 1750. However, ocean temperatures increased, especially in the mixed layer and current ocean vent flows may be higher now than in 1750. It would be better to define the anthropogenic ocean vent flux as the current difference between the ocean vent flow and the ocean absorption flow for cases where the former is larger than the latter. Change all text formulas accordingly. I don't think this makes a difference for the model calculations, but check this as well.
75. Note deleted.
76. Note for future revisions: Add 1st year of net ocean venting as result to the table.
77. Note for future revisions: Add ratio of societal savings / DACCS costs to the table
78. Note for future revisions: Replace chart with corrected values corresponding to those in table 6.
79. Note for future revisions: Start model in year 2025 or later and use extrapolated CO₂ sinks. This will increase total CO₂ to be sequestered but will reduce DACCS cost to more realistic values for the actual sequestration period.
80. Note for future revisions: Check for additional projects, check status and list references
81. Note for future revisions: Look up the fraction of CO₂ that remains in the top layer of the ocean (already in the list of references). Mention this in the text and add as a reference in the text. Change the default value for the "accessible" fraction of the ocean sink from the current 100% to a more realistic value based on the literature. Redo all calculations using this value. Change all tables and figures.
82. Dert, V. Savings and Avoided Costs of Living Carbon Negative. 2024 [\[Provide reference to e-Print publication.\]](#)
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86. Note for future revisions: Figures 8.2 and 8.3 need to be updated with newer values listed in table 8.4
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